

D6.3 – Report with empirical analysis of some of the incentives mapped in 6.2

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Glossary of terms

ACE	Angiotensin-converting-enzyme
ARB	Angiotensin II receptor blocker
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease of 2019 (caused by SARS-CoV-2)
CV	Coefficient of variation
DiD	Difference-in-Differences
DiD-C	Difference-in-Discontinuities
EQA	Quality-of-care standard indicator (<i>Estàndard de qualitat assistencial</i>)
FIMMG	Federazione Italiana Medici di Medicina Generale
GP	General practitioner
HbA1c	Glycated haemoglobin
HAV	Hepatitis A virus
HBV	Hepatitis B virus
HCV	Hepatitis C virus
HR	Hazard ratio
ICS	Catalan Health Institute
LDL	Low density lipoprotein
LHU	Local Health Unit
P4P	Pay-for-performance
PCP	Primary care practice
SISAP	Information System for Primary Care
T2DM	Type 2 diabetes mellitus

1. Executive summary

Using data from Spain and Italy, this report provides evidence to enhance understanding of how information provision and financial incentives influence quality-of-care in the primary care sector.

Long-term analyses (2010–2019) from the Catalan primary care system show that transparent, routinely updated feedback to professionals and financial incentives both contributed to improving quality-of-care and reducing practice variation. The benefits of information alone were similar to those of financial incentivisation, and adding incentivisation on top of information had a limited impact. Furthermore, derived indicators showed low responsiveness. These results underscore the need for careful design of quality improvement strategies.

A second study, leveraging the staggered post-COVID reinstatement of financial incentives, demonstrates how these mechanisms operate after system shocks. Early reintroduction of incentives doubled the likelihood of returning to pre-pandemic performance in the first two years, although information alone still supported steady recovery. Recovery varied by indicator type and practice characteristics, confirming the importance of tailored approaches and highlighting a higher resilience among smaller and rural practices.

Building on these findings, an ongoing prospective study tests the separate effects of withdrawing incentives and information on quality-of-care indicators. This will clarify whether information feedback can maintain quality in the absence of financial rewards and under which conditions performance declines.

The analysis conducted on data from the Italian primary care setting assesses the causal impact of introducing financial incentives to improve the quality of electronic records of clinical information for patients with diabetes. We find that an incentive targeting the quality of information can improve care quality, as measured by how regularly diabetes is monitored through glycated haemoglobin testing.

Overall, this report provides a number of insights for the design of incentives in the primary care setting. Information feedback is per se a powerful, scalable improvement tool, even in the absence of financial incentives; financial incentives add targeted value; in some cases, improvement in the quality of care can be achieved by providing incentives to improve the quality of health records; optimal quality-improvement schemes require strategic indicator selection, contextualization, and continuous performance monitoring.

2. Introduction

Quality of care measurement in primary care

Primary care is the first level of contact for the population with the public health system. It is responsible for addressing the main health problems in the community, providing preventive, curative, and rehabilitative services; such a role is essential for improving the health of the population and for preventing and reducing health costs.

All the resources destined to the multiple actors that constitute a health system, including primary care, are oriented towards a common goal: to improve the health of the population, which is at the center of the system [1]. Therefore, it is necessary to measure the quality of the service provided, since quality-of-care metrics are essential for understanding the status of the system, identifying weaknesses and monitoring the effects of improvement initiatives. Currently, quality-of-care measures are commonly reported as part of the reporting on the performance of health systems globally [2]. They are relevant for multiple stakeholders involved in processes like accreditation and certification, audit and feedback, public reporting, quality-based payments and the creation of tools to support clinical activity. Over the past 20 years, the interest in measuring quality has been accompanied and supported by an increased technical capacity to measure and analyse it, thanks to advances in information technologies.

Most quality measurement actions are related to the development and assessment of quality-of-care indicators [3]. Quality-of-care, which could be defined as “the degree to which health services for individuals and populations are effective, safe and people-centred” [4], is a theoretical concept that may include different elements depending on its exact definition and the context. Since this variable is difficult to measure, indicators are used as quantitative measures that provide information about the effectiveness, safety and/or people-centeredness of care [4]; such indicators contribute to have an exact conceptualization of quality. The concept of quality, and the indicators used to measure it, will vary depending on the care dimension, the healthcare system function (preventive, acute, chronic or palliative care) and the target of the assessed measure (professionals, payers, healthcare provider organisations, patients, etc.). Even though quality indicators may be diverse, there is a consensus that they are composed of three elements [5]:

- A denominator, describing the target population included.
- A numerator, describing the number of people in the denominator who have the specified intervention, treatment or outcome

- A description of the inclusions, exclusions and potential personalised care adjustments.

In addition to the above, institutions like the NHS Indicator Methodology and Assurance Service and the German Institute for Quality Assurance and Transparency in Health Care (IQTIG) have defined common attributes for them **[4–6]**:

1. A quality goal, a statement about the intended goal or objective (e.g. screening for diabetic foot should be done in all diabetic patients).
2. A measurement concept, a specified method of data collection and indicator calculation (e.g. % of diabetic population between 14 and 80 years old, with type-2 diabetes diagnosis, screened for diabetic foot in the last year).
3. An appraisal concept, a description of how this measure should be used to judge quality (e.g. if screening for diabetic foot is above 90%, this is considered to be good quality).

Strategies to improve quality-of-care: economic incentives and information provision

The fundamental goal of primary care professionals is to provide medical care with the aim of enhancing the well-being and health of their patients. However, it is widely acknowledged that, like professionals in other fields, various factors, including financial considerations, can impact their motivations and efforts (clinical practice) **[7,8]**. In recent decades, healthcare systems across Europe have increasingly turned to economic incentives as a means to strengthen primary care delivery and align it more closely with broader system objectives such as improved quality, efficiency, and coordination. This shift is rooted in the growing understanding that primary care functions as both a gatekeeper and a foundational component of effective health systems **[9, 10]**. Influenced by the principal-agent theory **[11,12]**, the rationale for these incentives lies in the ability to shape provider behaviour through structured rewards, thereby promoting the uptake of desired practices and policy priorities **[13,14]**.

In practice, a variety of incentive mechanisms have been implemented across European contexts. Notable early examples include the UK's Quality and Outcomes Framework (QOF), launched in 2004, and Germany's Disease Management Programs (DMPs), initiated in 2002. Both initiatives sought to link physician remuneration to performance, particularly in the management of chronic illnesses, by offering payments based on patient enrolment and compliance with predefined clinical protocols **[15-18]**.

Over time, many countries adopted similar approaches, though the models differ significantly in scope, financial magnitude, and administrative configuration. Some

schemes concentrate primarily on chronic disease management, while others incorporate a wider range of policy goals such as preventive care, equitable access, or patient satisfaction [19]. Financial incentives can range from modest supplementary payments to substantial bonuses constituting more than a quarter of a provider's earnings. Governance of these programs also varies, with some operating under national frameworks and others developed at regional or local levels.

Incentives may be monetary—such as pay-for-performance bonuses, capitation adjustments, or targeted subsidies for rural practice—or non-monetary, including professional recognition, improved work-life balance, or reduced bureaucratic load [20,21]. For instance, Portugal's Family Health Units incorporate both individual and team-based rewards that vary by organisational model [22], while in France, the ROSP program offers payments equivalent to around 10% of general practitioners' income [19]. These models aim to foster extrinsic motivation without undermining intrinsic professional values [23-24].

Among these strategies, pay-for-performance (P4P) has emerged as the most prevalent. It typically ties financial compensation to specific clinical or administrative benchmarks, often focusing on process and structural indicators rather than outcomes [25]. France's CAPI scheme stands out by integrating absolute performance, relative improvement, and peer comparisons within its bonus structure [19]. Coordination-focused incentives have also gained ground, particularly in systems like Germany, Denmark, and the Netherlands, where teams are rewarded for collaborative care planning and chronic disease management through hybrid models combining capitation with performance-based payments [21, 26].

Early research on financial incentives in chronic disease management, pioneered by Germany's Disease Management Programs (DMPs) in 2002, established a model for improving patient care integration and coordination [15]. This approach, which has since been adopted by countries like Denmark and the Netherlands [16, 18, 27], typically features a two-part incentive structure for primary care professionals. The first component is a capitation payment, where practitioners are compensated based on the number of patients with chronic conditions they enrol. The second component is a conditional payment, which is tied to the achievement of specific patient monitoring and care targets. This dual system, combining patient volume incentives with performance-based rewards, has become a common framework in the literature on disease management.

While evidence on the overall impact of these schemes is still inconclusive, with some studies pointing to modest gains in quality and others highlighting unintended consequences [28, 29], incentive programs continue to evolve. Their ongoing adaptation reflects efforts to tailor incentive design to national health priorities, resource constraints, and provider cultures. A comparative understanding of these diverse models is essential to identifying which

mechanisms most effectively support quality, equity, and sustainability in primary care.

Previous studies on P4P schemes have provided mixed results. Improvements are often modest and more pronounced in measures of processes than clinical outcomes **[30-34]**, and they tend to be restricted to targeted indicator sets **[35,36]**. Moreover, the effectiveness of P4P schemes is evolving slowly, and there is no clear evidence of progress in their design and evaluation over the years **[37]**. This highlights the need for further research into incentive schemes, particularly focusing on aspects of their design that can influence the behaviour of health professionals and health outcomes, such as the selection of an appropriate set of quality indicators. Notably, since this improvement initiative has been traditionally implemented simultaneously with other non-financial incentives (e.g., education, training, public reporting, feedback to professionals), attempts to isolate the causal impact of these incentives have encountered significant barriers **[31,38,39,40]**.

Although some studies have suggested that non-financial incentives have the potential to induce long-term practice changes where financial incentives may not **[41,42]**, further research into non-financial methods and their combination with P4P schemes is needed to explain their relative contribution.

Overall, the complexity of the interplay between financial and non-financial incentives is evident: while the first aim to align professional behavior with organizational goals by creating extrinsic rewards, the latter can leverage intrinsic motivation and reputational concerns **[39,40]**. As healthcare systems globally face the challenge of improving quality while managing costs, understanding the optimal balance between information-based and incentive-based approaches becomes crucial. In this report, we will consider two settings – the Catalan and a part of the Italian primary care system – with the aim of assessing the impact of different combinations of financial and informative incentives that were deployed in recent years.

Quality incentives in the Catalan and the Italian primary care systems

Since 2006, Catalonia, an autonomous community in northeastern Spain with over eight million inhabitants, has implemented a comprehensive quality improvement scheme in its public primary care system. It is based on the combination of information provision to professionals and financial incentives. The Catalan Health Institute (ICS), serving nearly 80% of the population across 272 primary care practices (PCPs), utilises the Quality-of-Care Standard (EQA) framework, comprising 118 evidence-based clinical indicators **[43]**. Professionals have real-time access to their EQA and other indicator results, as well as lists of patients not meeting specific criteria via a dedicated online platform (SISAP-ECAP, **Figure 1**). This platform is designed to foster self-assessment and intrinsic motivation for

quality improvement by enabling professionals to monitor their performance and compare it with peers (including the average results of their PCP, similar PCPs, and regional averages). Unlike UK's QOF, these results are not publicly reported, thereby reducing the impact of reputational concerns. Concurrently, the Management by Objectives (DPO) scheme offers financial incentives for meeting specific EQA targets, representing a classic P4P strategy. These targets are reviewed annually for each primary care professional, and they are adjusted based on prior indicator results. After almost two decades within these improvement schemes, many indicators stopped improving their initial results and plateaued, both in terms of result and variability across PCPs. Despite observing these trajectories, it is necessary to understand the specific effect that information and incentivization schemes have on the behavior of healthcare workers, and whether this impacted the quality of care provided. Determining the added value of financial incentivization over information to professionals and which professional and practice profiles benefit the most from these interventions remains a critical unresolved point that could significantly enhance cost-effectiveness estimates and policy decisions.

Figure 1 | Screenshot of SISAP-ECAP, the online platform informing professionals on quality-of-care indicator results.

As to the Italian system, incentivization of quality provision in primary care is highly fragmented, not only across regions – the level at which health care organisations are mainly managed – but also within regions. In particular, GPs operate on the basis of agreements signed with the relevant Local Health Authorities (LHU), which can contain, among other provisions, specific incentive mechanisms. In the part of this report dedicated to the Italian system, we use local operational agreements (*patti aziendali*) from the Province of Verona (Italy) to track institutional changes regarding the prevention and monitoring of diabetes. These agreements were established between GPs and LHUs to align clinical practice with regional priorities. The approach exploits a natural experiment from incentive scheme variation across Local Health Units (LHUs), with a focus on the 2014 extension of the targeted population for improving the completeness of electronic health records (EHRs). An interesting characteristic of this incentive scheme is that it combines elements of a financial incentive with information-related elements. Our focus will be on understanding whether providing financial incentives for improving the quality of the information system also has an impact on clinical outcomes.

3. Study on the impact of introducing financial incentives and information provision in Catalonia (Spain)¹

Study background

In Catalonia, the introduction of indicators into financial incentive and information schemes over time created a natural experiment to examine the individual and combined effects of information and incentivization within the same healthcare system, by analysing indicators that were simultaneously informed and incentivised, those only ever informed, and those initially informed and later incentivised.

This study examined the Catalan health system, which uniquely employs both information provision to professionals and P4P. We gathered evidence-based insights that disentangle the effects of information provision from those of financial incentives, assessing whether financial incentives provide incremental benefits beyond information alone and whether information feedback can drive improvements independently. We explored improvements not only in magnitude (quality of care) but also in consistency across practices (care equality), providing insights into which strategies are most effective at standardising care quality across a region. Such evidence could guide the strategic design of quality enhancement initiatives in primary care systems globally.

Hypothesis and aim

This study hypothesised that financial incentives and information provision can significantly impact the behaviour of health professionals, enhancing the quality of care.

Its aim was to understand how health workers responded to the introduction of an incentive and information system based on quality-of-care indicators.

Methodology

Study design

We analysed annual quality-of-care results (percentage achievement) and variability (coefficient of variation, CV) for all primary care practices (PCPs) in the

¹ The results of this part of the analysis were published in: Esteban-Fabro R, Coma E, Hermosilla E, Méndez-Boo L, Guiriguet C, Facchini G, Nicodemo C, Vidal-Alaball J. Information provision and financial incentives in Catalonia's public primary care (2010–2019): an interrupted time series analysis. *The Lancet Regional Health – Europe* 2024; 47: 101102.

Catalan Health Institute from 2010–2019. We focused on indicators that were newly introduced as *informed* (results visible on the online platform) or *incentivised* (informed plus financially rewarded) during this period. Using interrupted time series (ITS) regression, we assessed whether these policy changes produced significant immediate (step) or gradual (trend) effects on indicator performance and variability; these may result from rapid policy implementations or practice adjustments, or conversely, from a slower adaptation time, learning curves, or the need for cumulative patient visits to improve indicator results. Indicators were additionally classified as *newly created* or *derived* (constructed from subsets of pre-existing incentivised indicators), given the possibility that incentives on parent indicators may generate spillover effects and attenuate impacts on derived measures. For instance, EQA3110 ("LDL control in T2DM with high cardiovascular risk"), introduced as informed in 2017, was derived from the previously incentivised EQA0214 ("LDL control in patients with high cardiovascular risk"). We posited that incentives or information might have weaker effects on the first indicator.

Data sources and indicator calculation

Data for 92 adult-care indicators were extracted from the primary care information system (SISAP) at ICS, which covers all 272 PCPs and undergoes continuous multidisciplinary validation. To ensure consistency, all indicator results for 2010–2019 were recalculated using SISAP's current computation pipeline, including periods prior to an indicator's creation, when results were neither displayed to clinicians nor incentivised. We used a single annual measurement taken on December 31st to align with the pay-for-performance (P4P) evaluation cycle. Indicator results reflect the percentage of eligible patients receiving recommended care or achieving defined targets.

Indicator selection

To ensure data reliability, we applied a three-step quality filter. First, indicators were classified by the correlation between recalculated and historically reported results. Indicators with poor reproducibility (average Spearman's $r < 0.6$ and minimum $r < 0.5$) were excluded. Second, indicators lacking complete data for 2010–2019 were removed. Finally, two indicators with incorrect 2010 records were retained, but had 2010 values excluded. In total, 63 of 92 indicators (68.5%) were included.

Statistical analysis

For each indicator (Y_i), we adjusted an interrupted time series linear regression model (ITS) using the yearly indicator results (simple average of all PCPs) and coefficient of variation (CV of results in the PCPs), with the following formula,

$$(1) Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 time_i + \beta_2 intervention_i + \beta_3 time_i * intervention_i + e_i$$

where β_0 is the intercept of the pre-intervention trend, β_1 is the trend before the scheme change, β_2 is the step change in the first year after the intervention, and β_3 is the change in trend in the post-intervention period. *time* is a numerical variable indicating the year, and *intervention* is a dummy variable indicating whether the indicator was informed or incentivised that year, and e_i is the error term. For the seven indicators which were first informed and later incentivised, the following formula was used,

$$(2) Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 time_i + \beta_2 inform_i + \beta_3 time_i * inform_i + \beta_4 incent_i + \beta_5 time_i * incent_i + e_i$$

where β_4 and β_5 account for the assessment of incentivization effects over the informed period. In this case, *inform* and *incent* are dummy variables indicating whether an indicator was informed (*inform* = 1, *incent* = 0) or incentivised (*inform* = 1, *incent* = 1). Because the series contained only 10 time points and autocorrelation was minimal, we used lag-0 models and Newey–West standard errors to address potential heteroscedasticity. A logit-transformed sensitivity analysis examined robustness to ceiling effects.

Intervention effects were evaluated based on significant step changes or post-intervention trend changes. Indicators were classified as showing positive impact, negative impact, baseline improvement, or no effect. Analyses were performed in R 4.3.1 with $\alpha=0.05$.

Results

Incentive and information landscape

Among the 63 recalculated EQA indicators, 39 were introduced after 2013 (24 informed, 15 incentivised), each with at least three pre-intervention years (**Figure 2A**). Seven diagnostic indicators were first informed in 2013 and later incentivised in 2015. Fourteen indicators were incentivised throughout 2010–2019, and 10 were never informed or incentivised. Of the 19 derived indicators, 12 became informed, four incentivised, and three unchanged. Newly incentivised indicators mainly targeted control (7/15) and quaternary prevention (6/15), whereas newly informed indicators were mostly related to follow-up (8/24), diagnosis (7/24), or control (5/24).

Across indicators, information and incentivization were associated with rising performance and declining variability. Indicators incentivised throughout the decade showed steady improvement with evidence of plateauing, while indicators never informed nor incentivised showed no clear trends (**Figure 2B**).

Figure 2 | Landscape of EQA quality-of-care indicators included in the study. (A) Heatmap representing the scheme of incentivization and/or information for each of the 63 indicators studied during the period 2010-2019. Indicators are grouped by type of incentive scheme: always incentivised, introduced as incentivised, multiple changes (informed first and later incentivised), introduced as informed and never informed. Each indicator is colour-coded in grey if not informed, in yellow if informed and in a shade of blue depending on the number of points granted to that indicator in the incentive scheme (proportional to the amount of money provided). Derived indicators and the indicator type are indicated with the vertical annotation on the right. **(B)** Boxplot representation of the results (percentages of achievement) of 5 example indicators in all ICS primary care practices during the period 2010-2019. An indicator in each scheme category is depicted. The indicator introduction as informed or incentivised is represented with vertical dotted lines.

Impact of incentivization on newly introduced indicators

ITS linear regression analysis was used to determine the impact of incentivization and/or information on indicator results (the average percentage of achievement across PCPs) and variability (CV of indicator results) in the period 2010-2019 (**Figure 3, Annex Tables 1.1-1.2**). Before their introduction, 29 of 39 indicators (74%) already displayed upward trends, including similar proportions of derived and newly created indicators (**Annex Table 1.1**).

Among the 11 new indicators introduced as financially incentivised, seven (64%) showed positive impacts on results or variability (**Figure 3, Annex Table 1.1-1.2**). Four indicators exhibited significant post-intervention step increases (1.07–19.67 percentage points), and four showed positive trend changes (0.34–1.09 percentage point improvements per year). A total of six indicators showed overall positive effects on results (**Figure 3, Annex Table 1.1**). Variability improved for five indicators, including four with significant step reductions (–0.14 to –0.01 CV) and one with a favourable trend reduction (–0.03 CV per year) (**Figure 3, Annex Table 1.2**). Notably, most indicators without detected effects were already improving before incentivization.

Effect of information (without incentives) on new indicators

Information alone produced positive impacts for 9 of 12 newly created indicators (75%), spanning diagnosis, treatment, quaternary prevention, and follow-up activities (**Figure 3, Annex Table 1.1-1.2**). Six indicators showed improved post-intervention trends (1.25–6.66 percentage points per year), and four of them had significant step increases in addition (1.25–8.87 percentage points). Variability improved in seven indicators via step reductions (–0.18 to –0.001 CV) and in seven through favourable trend changes (–0.05 to –0.004 CV). Indicators without detected effects had significantly favourable pre-intervention trajectories.

For the seven diagnostic indicators first informed in 2013 and then incentivised in 2015, information positively affected six (**Figure 3, Annex Table 1.1-1.2**). Incentivization did not produce additional significant step or trend improvements in results or variability. This suggests limited incremental value of incentivization after a period of information-based exposure. These findings suggest that while both information and incentivization strategies can improve indicator performance, the additional impact of incentivization after a period of information may be limited.

Derived indicators, always-incentivised indicators, and never-incentivised indicators

Among the 16 derived indicators—expected to experience spillover from parent indicators—positive impacts were less common: only five (31%) improved in results or variability after the interventions (**Figure 3, Annex Table 1.1-1.2**). One incentivised derived indicator showed a significant CV reduction, and two informed derived indicators showed step increases in results. However, most derived indicators already exhibited strong pre-intervention improvements (12 with rising results; 14 with declining variability).

Figure 3 | Summary of results from the interrupted time series regression analysis. (A) Summary heatmap of the 39 indicators analysed with ITS, grouped according to their incentivization patterns. The ITS-derived impact of information and incentivization on results (average percentage of achievement across PCPs) and variability (CV of indicator results) is FLASH – Flexible Approaches to Support Health through financing

specified for each indicator. Effects have been classified as *positive*, *negative*, *no effect* and *baseline improvement* (if positive pre-intervention trends remain unaffected post-intervention; see **Methods** for more). **(B, C)** Example ITS analyses on indicator results **(B)** and variability **(C)** in the form of dot plots depicting an example indicator from each of the three heatmap blocks (*new indicators*, *multiple changes*, and *derived indicators*). Linear regression lines are shown for the pre- and post-intervention periods, along with their slopes.

Finally, we assessed unexpected factors impacting indicator results and variability by simulating an intervention in 2014 for the 24 indicators that did not undergo a scheme change during the study period (14 always incentivised and 10 never informed nor incentivised). The ITS analysis revealed positive step changes in the results of two of the 14 always incentivised indicators (14%), one of which also showed a significant improvement in variability (Figure 4, Annex Tables 3-4). None of the 10 indicators that were never informed nor incentivised showed positive effects. The effects of information and incentivization on indicator results were validated in a sensitivity analysis accounting for potential ceiling effects (Data available in the published manuscript [44]).

Figure 4 | Summary of results from the interrupted time series regression analysis using always incentivised and never informed indicators and simulating an intervention in 2014. Heatmap of the 24 indicators analysed with ITS, where the impact of information and incentivization on results and variability is specified for each indicator.

Study conclusions

In this study, we observed that from 2010 to 2019, **information and incentivization had similar positive impacts** on quality-of-care **indicators**. However, their effects may depend on the type of indicators and on previous interventions on them or their parent indicators.

- **Incentivization** was associated with an **improvement** in quality-of-care indicator results and/or variability among **new indicators (7/11, 64%)**.
- **Information without incentivization** was linked to an **improvement** in quality-of-care indicator results and/or variability among **new indicators (9/12, 75%)**.
- **Incentivization after information** was not associated with further step or trend improvements on 7 diagnostic indicators.
- **Indicators derived from other incentivised indicators** may be influenced by the original indicators (**spillover effect**) and thus **benefit the least from information or incentivization**.

4. Study on the impact of information provision and financial incentives in the recovery of primary care quality after a health system shock (COVID-19 pandemic)²

Study background

COVID-19 emerged in Wuhan in late 2019 and rapidly escalated into a global pandemic [45], causing severe strain on health systems worldwide [46]. In Catalonia, as in many regions, primary care played a central role in triage and case management, while simultaneously facing major disruptions to routine care. During 2020, the Catalan Health Institute (ICS) recorded marked declines in quality-of-care indicators related to follow-up, control, and screening of chronic conditions (Figure 5) [47]. In response to these challenges, the existing pay-for-performance (P4P) scheme was temporarily suspended: although indicator results continued to be displayed to professionals, financial incentives were automatically awarded to all staff to acknowledge the extraordinary demands of the pandemic, and therefore they were not linked to specific indicator results.

Figure 5 | Drop in quality-of-care indicator results at the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic in Catalonia.

Source: Coma E *et al.*, BMC Primary Care 2020²⁸.

² The results of this part of the analysis will be published in: Esteban-Fabró R, Coma E, Marin-Gomez FX, Hermsilla E, Méndez-Boo L, Guiriguet C, Facchini G, Violán C, Nicodemo C, Vidal-Alaball J. Financial incentives and information provision for post-pandemic primary care quality recovery: a longitudinal study in Catalonia. *The British Journal of General Practice* 2026; Accepted for publication in November 2025, in press.

Post-pandemic, ICS launched a phased quality-of-care recovery strategy, re-introducing only 13 previously incentivised indicators into the P4P scheme while maintaining information feedback for all indicators. This staggered re-introduction created a natural experiment to disentangle the effects of information provision and financial incentives on the recovery of quality-of-care in primary care. Using a retrospective observational design covering 2019–2024, this study evaluated whether financial incentives enhanced quality-of-care recovery beyond information alone and whether information feedback can independently drive improvements. The findings aim to support evidence-based decisions in the design and optimisation of primary care performance strategies.

Hypotheses and aims

In this study, we had the following hypotheses:

- The **recovery of indicator results** after the pandemic was influenced by **information provision** and **economic incentive schemes**.
- The **effect of incentives and information** on indicator recovery varied based on **PCP, population and health professional features**.

The **general aim** of the study was to provide a **comprehensive analysis** of the **impact of economic incentives and information provision** on the **post-COVID-19 recovery of quality-of-care indicators** in PCPs in Catalonia. We had the following specific aims:

1. To compare **the recovery** of quality-of-care indicators following the COVID-19 decline between **indicators that were economically incentivised early** and **those that were not**.
2. To analyse specific **patterns of recovery among PCPs** and identify **population and PCP characteristics** associated with these patterns.

Methodology

Study design

This retrospective longitudinal study used data from 37 quality-of-care indicators across 287 PCPs managed by ICS (2019–2024). Thirteen were re-incentivised in 2021 (“Early-incentivised”); the remaining 24 were re-incentivised in 2023 (“Late-incentivised”), having only been reported to professionals until then. Recovery was assessed via: (a) year-over-year percentage change (mean % change and coefficient of variation [CV]); (b) intra-annual % change (January–December); and (c) time to recovery, the months from January 2021 until results returned to the pre-pandemic range. The relationship between incentive status and recovery time was analysed

using a mixed-effects Cox proportional hazards model. Unsupervised clustering identified recovery patterns among PCPs. All 287 PCPs managed by ICS with complete indicator reporting were included; no additional sampling or recruitment pathway of individual professionals or patients was required, as the study relied on routinely collected practice-level administrative data.

Data sources and outcome calculations

Monthly indicator data from the EQA framework [43] were obtained at the PCP level from SISAP databases. The study covered January 2019–December 2024, with 2019 as the pre-pandemic reference. SISAP provided indicator features (e.g., incentive status, type) and PCP characteristics (e.g., socioeconomic deprivation index [48] rurality, demographics, workforce size). No missing data were identified for the selected indicators or PCPs during the study period, as these routinely monitored indicators are validated and curated for clinical and management purposes.

Time to recovery was calculated projecting 2019 monthly results, except for EQA0403, where 2018 values were used. Recovery was the number of months from January 2021 until the average PCP result (with 95% CI) re-entered and remained within the 2019 range for six consecutive months. Indicators unaffected by the pandemic showed negative recovery times; those unrecovered by December 2024 were assigned 60 months for graphical/clustering use, but excluded from other analyses. For PCP-level analysis, 2019 projections used each PCP's monthly values, with confidence intervals from the standard deviation across all PCPs.

Indicator selection

Indicators were included if they: (1) had high EQA evidence [43]; (2) were financially incentivised for ≥ 5 years pre-pandemic; (3) focused on adults (>14 years); and (4) were re-incentivised between 2021–2024. The 37 selected indicators (**Annex Table 2.1**) spanned control, diagnosis, follow-up, screening, treatment, and vaccination (**Annex Table 2.2**). Of these, 13 (35%) were re-incentivised in 2021 (“Early-incentivised”; 7 control, 3 screening, 3 treatment). The remaining two of the 15 priority indicators were excluded based on the selection criteria. Although 2021 P4P funds were ultimately distributed universally as a pandemic reward, professionals were exposed to the P4P stimulus and unaware of the distribution change until the last quarter of 2021. The remaining 24 indicators (65%) were informed but unincentivised until 2023 (“Late-incentivised”; 7 diagnosis, 7 treatment, 5 screening, 2 control, 2 follow-up, 1 vaccination).

Statistical analysis

A mixed-effects Cox proportional hazards model estimated the effect of incentives on recovery likelihood, accounting for covariates and data hierarchy. Covariates were selected via bivariate analyses (**Annex Table 3**). The model:

$$h_{ij}(t) = h_{0k}(t) \exp(\beta_1 \text{IncentiveScheme}_{ij} + \beta_2 \% \text{ResultDrop}_{ij} + b_{0j})$$

where $h_{ij}(t)$ is the recovery hazard at time t for indicator i in practice j , $h_{0k}(t)$ the baseline hazard by indicator type k , $\text{IncentiveScheme}_{ij}$ the incentive exposure, $\% \text{ResultDrop}_{ij}$ the post-COVID-19 drop, and $b_{0j} \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$ a PCP-level random intercept. The model stratified by indicator type and included a random effect for PCPs. Schoenfeld residuals were inspected to assess proportional hazards.

K-means clustering (R *stats* package) of PCP-level recovery times was applied separately for early- and late-incentivised indicators. The optimal number of clusters ($K=2$) was chosen using within-cluster sum of squares and silhouette width, classifying PCPs into four recovery profiles: fast recoverers, fast for incentivised, fast for informed, and slow recoverers. Profiles were characterised by contextual and organisational variables.

Descriptive statistics summarised trends. Normality guided parametric (t-tests, ANOVA) or non-parametric (Wilcoxon, Kruskal-Wallis) tests for group comparisons. Spearman's rank correlation assessed continuous associations, and chi-square or Fisher's exact tests were used for categorical comparisons. False discovery rate correction addressed multiple testing, with significance set at 0.05. Analyses and visualisations were performed in R 4.3.1.

Results

The impact of early incentivization on initial indicator responses

We analyzed quality-of-care indicator data from 287 PCPs in Catalonia: 100 (35%) rural and 187 (65%) urban, including 56 (19.5%) in highly deprived areas. The average population per PCP was 18,295 (21,318 in urban vs. 12,641 in rural PCPs, $p < 0.001$). Mean patient age was 49 years (48.5 vs. 50, $p < 0.001$), 50.6% were females (51.3% vs. 49.3%, $p < 0.001$) and 18.4% immigrants (19.8% vs. 15.9%, $p < 0.001$). PCPs averaged 26.6 professionals (29.8 urban vs. 20.7 rural, $p < 0.001$).

In 2020, 35 of 37 indicators (95%) dropped significantly in results and/or increased variability (CV) compared to 2019 (average 15.26% drop and 115.6% CV increase; **Figure 6**); only 2 treatment indicators did not. Early-incentivised indicators started recovering sooner: by December 2021, 11/13 (85%) showed improvements, defined as statistically significant increases in indicator value and/or decreases in variability compared to the previous year, rising to 12/13 (92%) in 2022 and sustaining gains

through 2024 (Figure 6). In contrast, late-incentivised indicators improved later: only 5/24 (21%) improved by 2021, increasing to 13/24 (54%) in 2022, when still only informed. Once reintroduced to P4P in 2023, 20/24 (83%) improved, with sustained gains in 2024 (Figure 6).

Figure 6 | Summary of year-to-year changes for all the assessed indicators. Heatmap depicting the outcomes of the analysis of the % change from the previous year for all indicators (early- and late-incentivised), both in terms of indicator variability (CV, left block) and results (right block) across PCPs. Green cells represent significantly positive changes from the previous year, red cells depict significantly negative changes, and grey cells represent years where no significant change was detected. The right column indicates the type of indicator, as explained in Methods.

Recovery times among early- and late-incentivised indicators

We assessed differences in indicator average recovery times between treatment arms (Figure 7). By December 2024, 11/13 (85%) early-incentivised indicators had returned to 2019 levels, compared to 12/24 (50%) late-incentivised indicators. Among recovered indicators, average recovery times were not significantly different (21.9 months for early-incentivised vs. 17.5 months for late-incentivised, p=0.45). However, treatment indicators recovered significantly faster than control indicators (4.7 vs. 28.6 months, p<0.05).

Early-incentivised indicators, while showing higher recovery rates, also experienced steeper 2020 declines (-24.3% vs. -9.2% for late-incentivised indicators, $p < 0.05$), suggesting greater pandemic impact (Figure 7). The severity of the drop also varied by indicator type: control, screening, and follow-up indicators saw the largest declines (25%, 21.7%, 18.1% in 2019 results, respectively), while diagnosis, treatment, and vaccination indicators were less affected (9.4%, 3.5%, 1.5%; $p < 0.05$ for treatment vs. control/screening, Figure 7).

Figure 7 | Time to recovery and 2020 result drops for all indicators. Lollipop plot representing the average recovery times (in months since January 2021) of all indicators (left panel, faceted by financial incentive scheme) and the average % drop in results during the pandemic (right panel). Colours represent indicator types, and dot shapes their recovery status (recovered or not, 2019 results).

Using the recovery times across PCPs, we identified PCPs that recovered results by December 2024, those that did not, and those that had already recovered before January 2021 for each indicator (**Figure 8**). Early-incentivised indicators had higher numbers of PCPs dropping results during the pandemic (lower % of PCPs recovered before 2021 vs. late-incentivised indicators, $p < 0.01$). However, a higher percentage of the PCPs that dropped early-incentivised indicator results recovered them before December 2024 ($p < 0.01$ vs. late-incentivised indicators). Although late-incentivised indicators had more PCPs unable to recover results in the study period ($p < 0.05$ vs. early-incentivised, **Figure 8**), a higher percentage of the PCPs that recovered the results of late-incentivised indicators did so before 2023, when they were only informed ($p < 0.001$).

Further stratification by indicator types revealed differences in recovery patterns: while most PCPs already showed recovered results for treatment and vaccination indicators during 2020, this was not the case for the rest of indicators. Among control and screening indicators, those incentivised early were able to recover dropped results in almost all the PCPs, while those incentivised late had higher rates of PCP that did not recover. Around a third of PCPs did not manage to recover diagnostic indicator results, all of which were incentivised in 2023.

Figure 8 | Percentage of PCPs that recovered and did not recover per indicator. (A) Barplot representing the number of PCPs for each indicator that recovered results (green, with pale green being PCPs that recovered during the only informed period), those that did not recover during the study period (red), and those that had already recovered at the beginning of the follow-up (January 2021) or never dropped results (yellow). Green numbers represent the % of recovered PCPs per indicator. The top panel includes the early-incentivised indicators, and the late-incentivised are in the bottom panel. (B) Boxplots comparing the differences in the % of PCPs that dropped results in 2020 and then recovered (left panel), the % of PCPs that did not recover (center panel) and the % of PCPs recovered before 2021 (right panel). P-values represent the result of Mann-Whitney-Wilcoxon tests.

To assess the impact of early financial incentivization on the recovery of quality-of-care indicators, we fit a mixed-effects Cox proportional hazards model using recovery time data (per indicator and PCP) from January 2021 to December 2022. During this period, late-incentivised indicators remained informed, allowing a direct comparison between incentivised and informed indicators. Initial bivariate analyses (**Annex Table 2.3**) showed a significantly greater drop in results among incentivised indicators, which were also more frequently control indicators, with no diagnostic or follow-up indicators represented. The Cox model included the incentive scheme and the 2020 result drop as covariates, was stratified by indicator type, and included a random effect for primary care practice to account for clustering and unmeasured heterogeneity (see Methods). Indicators that remained incentivised during 2021–2022 had a significantly higher recovery likelihood (HR = 2.06; 95% CI, 1.88–2.25), indicating a 106% greater probability of recovery at any time point than informed-only indicators, adjusting for baseline drop and clustering. Greater 2020 result drops were associated with slower recovery (HR = 0.988; 95% CI, 0.986–0.990).

Recovery patterns among PCPs

To identify recovery patterns across PCPs, we applied unsupervised K-means clustering to 2021–2024 recovery time data by PCP and indicator. Based on results across incentivised and informed indicators, four PCP clusters were defined: fast recoverers (low recovery times for both types of indicators), fast for incentivised, fast for informed and slow recoverers (with the highest overall recovery times) (**Figure 9**).

Fast and fast for incentivised recoverers showed quicker recovery for 10/13 (77%) incentivised indicators ($p < 0.05$ vs. other clusters). Fast recoverers also recovered 13/24 (54%) of the late-incentivised indicators (12 indicators vs. *slow* and 10 vs. *fast for incentivised* PCPs, $p < 0.05$), spanning 6 diagnostic, 3 screening, 2 control, 1 follow-up and 1 treatment indicator. Fast for informed recoverers showed better recovery only in 5/24 indicators (21%, 4 diagnostic and 1 screening). No consistent differences in recovery times were observed between clusters for the 10 treatment indicators, where many PCPs had already recovered by 2021.

Cluster characterisation (**Table 1**) revealed enrichment of rural PCPs among fast and fast for informed clusters (50% each vs. 32% and 23% of *fast for incentivised* and *slow* PCPs). Fast recoverers also had smaller assigned populations (avg. 16,230 vs. 20,348 in slow PCPs), fewer professionals (24.8 vs. 28.6 in slow PCPs), and lower 2020 drops (11% vs. 14.7–16% among the rest).

Figure 9 | Classification of PCPs based on recovery patterns found with unsupervised clustering. Heatmap of scaled recovery times for all indicators among the 4 classes of PCPs that were defined by unsupervised clustering (see Methods). Blue indicates low recovery time values, and red represents high values. Top annotations indicate the PCP rural/urban and MEDEA socioeconomic deprivation index for urban areas (4U to 1U, from most to least deprived). Right annotations represent indicator types and significant differences in indicator recovery times among clusters: columns represent paired comparisons, and the degree of orange is proportional to p-value significance below 0.05 (Dunn's post-hoc test).

Table 1 | Summary of the associations between recovery profiles and the sociodemographic and organisational characteristics of PCPs.

	Fast	Fast for incentivised	Fast for informed	Slow	p.over all
	N=66	N=72	N=36	N=112	
MEDEA socioeconomic deprivation index					
1U	4 (6.06%)	10 (13.9%)	3 (8.33%)	27 (24.1%)	
2U	12 (18.2%)	10 (13.9%)	2 (5.56%)	15 (13.4%)	
3U	7 (10.6%)	11 (15.3%)	9 (25%)	21 (18.8%)	
4U	10 (15.2%)	18 (25.0%)	4 (11.1%)	23 (20.5%)	
Rural	33 (50.0%)	23 (31.9%)	18 (50.0%)	26 (23.2%)	
N patients	16,230 (8,163)	17,838 (7,785)	16,840 (8,731)	20,348 (7,755)	0.005
Age of patients	49.5 (1.81)	48.8 (1.73)	48.9 (2.24)	48.9 (1.91)	0.177
% female patients	50.2 (1.67)	50.7 (1.58)	50.2 (2.26)	50.9 (2.53)	0.139
% immigrant patients	16.7 (7.24)	18.2 (8.88)	20.3 (8.56)	19.1 (9.76)	0.202
N professionals	24.8 (10.9)	26.3 (9.66)	24.8 (10.6)	28.6 (9.40)	0.046
N general practitioners	12.3 (5.46)	13.1 (4.97)	12.4 (5.40)	14.4 (4.77)	0.035
N nurses	12.5 (5.53)	13.2 (4.74)	12.4 (5.20)	14.3 (4.68)	0.063
Avg % drop in 2019 results	-11.02 (4.70)	-14.83 (4.24)	-14.74 (3.76)	-16.04 (3.67)	<0.001

N represents the number of observations. MEDEA classification stratifies urban PCPs according to the socioeconomic deprivation of the area they serve, ranked from 1U to 4U (from less to more deprived, respectively).

Study conclusions

In this study, we observed that **incentives can accelerate post-shock quality-of-care recovery**, but their effectiveness varies by indicator and practice characteristics. Furthermore, **tailored strategies are needed**: combining financial and informational approaches, adapted to PCP context and indicator type, may yield more resilient recovery trajectories.

- **Early financial incentives accelerated recovery:** Early-incentivised indicators recovered faster and had over twice the likelihood of returning to pre-pandemic levels compared with late-incentivised indicators, despite larger pandemic-related declines.
- **Information provision supported gradual recovery:** Among late-incentivised indicators, many PCPs showed improvement during the information-only period, indicating that transparent feedback alone can support progress.
- **Recovery differed by indicator type and practice context:**
 - *Indicator type:* Treatment indicators were least affected and recovered fastest, while diagnostic indicators recovered more slowly.
 - *PCP profile:* Faster-recovering PCPs tended to be rural, smaller, and experienced milder drops; slower-recovering ones were typically urban, larger, and experienced deeper declines.

5. Study on the retrieval of economic incentives and information provision on quality-of-care indicators for primary care³

Study background

Pay-for-performance (P4P) schemes are widely used to improve primary care quality, yet their true effectiveness remains uncertain because financial incentives are often implemented alongside other interventions—especially continuous information feedback—which makes their individual effects on specific quality-of-care indicators difficult to disentangle. In Catalonia, where the ICS has long combined real-time performance feedback with financial incentives, prior analyses suggest that both mechanisms can drive quality improvements; however, the results of quality-of-care indicators plateau over time. There is an unmet need to clarify the added value of incentives beyond information alone on each indicator. To address this evidence gap, we designed a prospective study specifically to isolate the effects of removing financial incentives and, separately, removing information feedback, thereby enabling a rigorous assessment of their independent and combined contributions to quality of care across different indicator types and potential spillover pathways.

Hypotheses and aims

In this study, we hypothesised that economic incentives and information are effective measures for improving the quality of care, and their removal will result in a decline in quality-of-care indicators. Specifically, we hypothesised that:

1. The **removal of economic incentives** will have a **different effect** depending on the **type of indicator**.
2. The **reductions** observed in (1) will be **more pronounced** if **information** about the results is **also removed**.
3. The **reductions** will be **smaller** for disease indicators that have other incentivised or informed indicators (spillover).
4. Changes in the **patterns of indicator recording** will occur.

The general aim of this study was to assess the impact of retrieving economic incentives and information provision on quality-of-care indicators among primary care professionals. The specific aims were:

1. To analyse the **effect of retrieving the economic incentives** linked to indicators.
2. To analyse the **effect of the retrieval of the information** provision linked to indicators.
3. To analyse the effects of Aims #1 and #2 based on the **type of indicator**.
4. To evaluate **possible spillover effects** on other indicators.

³ Study registration: ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT06829589.

5. To evaluate **changes in the registering activity** of healthcare professionals.

Methodology

Study setting and population

The study is conducted among GPs and nurses in 68 primary care practices (PCPs) across three ICS health management areas (Catalunya Central, Penedès, Girona). These regions were selected after agreement with territorial managers and PCP directors. Eligible participants are professionals with sufficient clinical activity to be included in ICS' pay-for-performance (P4P) scheme. PCPs with very low baseline quality-of-care scores (EQA [43] <600) were excluded. Recruitment occurred between December 2024 and January 2025.

Study design and interventions

We implemented a prospective study with three experimental arms to assess the impact of removing financial incentives and information feedback for seven quality-of-care indicators. Randomization was performed at PCP level into the following arms (**Figure 10**):

- **Control:** standard P4P scheme with full indicator feedback through the SISAP-ECAP online platform (**Figure 11A**).
- **Intervention 1:** removal of financial incentives for the seven indicators; scores for these indicators are no longer considered in the P4P scheme (**Figure 11B**), but professionals receive the equivalent monetary amount directly at the end of the year, maintaining their total compensation while decoupling payment from performance on those seven measures.
- **Intervention 2:** same incentive removal as Intervention 1 plus removal of indicator-level information feedback (numeric result, trend plots, achievement level, and number of unmet cases). Only patient lists remain visible as clinical decision-support tools (**Figure 11C**).

To ensure patient safety, Intervention 2 is suspended if any indicator's average performance falls below 10% of the control group for four consecutive weeks.

Figure 10 | Study design. Primary care professionals were randomized at the practice (PCP) level into three study arms: (1) control group, with no changes to the existing incentive and information structure; (2) intervention group 1, in which financial incentives tied to seven specific indicators were removed; and (3) intervention group 2, which mirrored intervention 1 but also removed feedback on the corresponding indicators from the professionals’ online platform. The study duration is from February to December 2025, when continuous weekly monitoring of results will be performed. Final analysis of the study outcomes will be done at the end of that period.

A Control arm

SISAP - ECAP
Monitoring clinical indicators for primary care professionals

+ Legend List of prioritized patients

Indicators: All Unfavorable Chosen Detection

NOTIF. ECAP	Indicator	Result	Unresolved patients		
			Evolution 4 months	Current	Points
Synthetic		100%			719,8 of 1.000
Cardiovascular disease					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0201 Adequacy of treatment of atrial fibrillation	78,57		3	0 of 30,13 +
	EQA0202 Control of anticoagulant treatment	50		1	informative +
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0203 Antiplatelet treatment in IHD/CVA	96,88		1	30,13 of 30,13 +
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0204 LDL control in IHD/CVA/Claud+T2DM	55		9	28,05 of 28,05 +
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0205 BP control in IHD/CVA	60		8	0 of 29,1 +
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0206 Treatment with beta-blockers for IHD/heart failure	100		0	informative +
+ EQA0207	Treatment with ACE inhibitors or ARBs	81,82		4	27,02 of 27,02 +
+ EQD0238	Diagnostic adequacy of cardiovascular disease	64,1		14	20,78 of 20,78 +
Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM)					
	EQA0208 T2DM: diabetic foot screening	67,8		19	6,76 of 27,02 +
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0209 T2DM: HbA1C control	57,63		25	0 of 29,1 +
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0210 T2DM: retinopathy screening	77,08		11	0 of 29,1 +
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0212 BP control in T2DM	80,7		11	28,05 of 28,05 +
+ EQD0239	Diagnostic quality of T2DM	95,61		5	20,78 of 20,78 +
EQA0248	Pneumococcal vaccination coverage in people with diabetes mellitus	39,13		42	16,63 of 16,63 +

B Intervention 1

NOTIF. ECAP	Indicator	Result	Unresolved patients		
			Evolution 4 months	Current	Points
Synthetic		100%			719,8 of 1.000
Cardiovascular disease					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0201 Adequacy of treatment of atrial fibrillation	78,57		3	0 of 30,13 +
	EQA0202 Control of anticoagulant treatment	50		1	informative +
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0203 Antiplatelet treatment in IHD/CVA	96,88		1	30,13 of 30,13 +
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0204 LDL control in IHD/CVA/Claud+T2DM	55		9	28,05 of 28,05 +
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0205 BP control in IHD/CVA	60		8	informative +
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0206 Treatment with beta-blockers for IHD/heart failure	100		0	informative +
+ EQA0207	Treatment with ACE inhibitors or ARBs	81,82		4	27,02 of 27,02 +
+ EQD0238	Diagnostic adequacy of cardiovascular disease	64,1		14	20,78 of 20,78 +
Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM)					
	EQA0208 T2DM: diabetic foot screening	67,8		19	6,76 of 27,02 +
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0209 T2DM: HbA1C control	57,63		25	0 of 29,1 +
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0210 T2DM: retinopathy screening	77,08		11	0 of 29,1 +
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0212 BP control in T2DM	80,7		11	informative +
+ EQD0239	Diagnostic quality of T2DM	95,61		5	20,78 of 20,78 +
EQA0248	Pneumococcal vaccination coverage in people with diabetes mellitus	39,13		42	16,63 of 16,63 +

C Intervention 2

NOTIF. ECAP	Indicator	Result	Unresolved patients		
			Evolution 4 months	Current	Points
Synthetic		100%			719,8 of 1.000
Cardiovascular disease					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0201 Adequacy of treatment of atrial fibrillation	78,57		3	0 of 30,13 +
	EQA0202 Control of anticoagulant treatment	50		1	informative +
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0203 Antiplatelet treatment in IHD/CVA	96,88		1	30,13 of 30,13 +
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0204 LDL control in IHD/CVA/Claud+T2DM	55		9	28,05 of 28,05 +
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0205 BP control in IHD/CVA	60		8	informative +
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0206 Treatment with beta-blockers for IHD/heart failure	100		0	informative +
+ EQA0207	Treatment with ACE inhibitors or ARBs	81,82		4	27,02 of 27,02 +
+ EQD0238	Diagnostic adequacy of cardiovascular disease	64,1		14	20,78 of 20,78 +
Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM)					
	EQA0208 T2DM: diabetic foot screening	67,8		19	6,76 of 27,02 +
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0209 T2DM: HbA1C control	57,63		25	0 of 29,1 +
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0210 T2DM: retinopathy screening	77,08		11	0 of 29,1 +
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EQA0212 BP control in T2DM	80,7		11	informative +
+ EQD0239	Diagnostic quality of T2DM	95,61		5	20,78 of 20,78 +
EQA0248	Pneumococcal vaccination coverage in people with diabetes mellitus	39,13		42	16,63 of 16,63 +

Figure 11 | Visualisation of the information platform among the study arms. Health professionals were randomised to three intervention arms. **(A)** The control arm has no changes in the information and P4P schemes. **(B)** Intervention 1 involves the removal of financial incentives associated with 7 indicators. There are no longer points linked to those indicators (they reflect the relative weight of each indicator in the overall scheme); therefore, they are *informative* in the Points section. **(C)** Intervention 2 combines the removal of both financial incentives, like intervention 1, plus the removal of information provision: the numeric result, evolution plot, and points are hidden. However, the list of patients not fulfilling indicator criteria is maintained.

Study period and sample

The study runs from February to December 2025, aligned with the P4P evaluation calendar. Sample-size calculations indicated a need for 36 clusters; 68 PCPs were randomised, and 5 withdrew post-randomisation, resulting in 24 control, 19 Intervention 1, and 20 Intervention 2 PCPs (710 GPs and 723 nurses, **Figure 12**).

Figure 12 | Randomisation flowchart. From the 69 eligible PCPs in the territories of Catalunya Central, Girona and Penedès, one PCP was excluded due to a low value of the synthetic quality-of-care EQA indicator (<600). The remaining 68 PCPs were randomised to the three treatment arms. However, 5 PCPs requested to be excluded from the study, leaving 24 PCPs in the control arm, 19 in Intervention 1, and 20 in Intervention 2.

Indicator selection

Seven indicators were selected based on variation over time, inter-PCP variability, denominator size, and complexity (rated by an advisory group). All hypertension-related indicators were included to test for spillover effects (**Table 2**).

Table 2 | Indicators included in the study.

Indicator name	Difference in result, Dec. 2024 vs. 2023 (95% CI)		Coefficient of variation (Dec. 2024)	Average population per PCP, Dec. 2024 (min, max)		Complexity
Blood pressure control in diabetes	2.21	(1.49, 2.92)	3.42	950.86	(187, 2661)	4
Blood pressure control in ischemic heart disease / cerebrovascular accident	2.88	(1.7, 4.06)	5.44	438.06	(78, 1161)	4
Hypertension: Blood pressure control in patients with chronic kidney disease	2.12	(1.21, 3.03)	4.30	251.53	(47, 646)	4
Hypertension: Blood pressure control	2.66	(1.78, 3.54)	8.54	1484.83	(271, 3902)	3
Diagnostic adequacy of hypertension	1.90	(-0.29, 4.08)	9.75	159.2	(30, 450)	3
Appropriate treatment of atrial fibrillation	0.94	(0.45, 1.43)	2.09	264.31	(42, 775)	2
Inhaler verification	8.39	(6.4, 10.39)	7.45	161.73	(31, 471)	1

Outcome measures and covariates

The **primary outcome** measure is the monthly result of the seven quality-of-care indicators. It is calculated as the % of achievement (% of patients assigned to that professional who fulfil the indicator criteria in relation to all the patients who should receive that clinical activity).

Covariates related to PCPs, professionals, and patients will be included:

- Practice rurality: Urban PCPs are considered those in municipalities with >10,000 inhabitants and a population density >150 inhabitants/km², as per regional guidelines. The rest are considered rural PCPs.
- Socioeconomic status: it will be measured using the validated socioeconomic index from the Catalan Agency for Healthcare Quality and Assessment (AQUAS) [49].
- Percentage of female patients in the PCP assigned population.
- Percentage of immigrant patients in the PCP assigned population.
- Number of professionals in the PCP (GPs and nurses).
- Number of patients assigned to the PCP.
- Sex of the professional.
- Age of the professional.
- Years worked at ICS.

To avoid potential sources of bias, the randomisation of PCPs into the study arms ensured that the baseline primary outcome measures and the PCP-level covariables were balanced. The balance between arms was maintained despite the exclusion of the 5 PCPs after the study start (Table 3).

Table 3 | PCP variables and indicator results among treatment arms.

	Control N=24	Intervention 1 N=19	Intervention 2 N=20	p.over all
Region:				0.996
Catalunya Central	9 (37.5%)	8 (42.1%)	8 (40.0%)	
Girona	9 (37.5%)	6 (31.6%)	7 (35.0%)	
Penedès	6 (25.0%)	5 (26.3%)	5 (25.0%)	
Rurality:				0.666
Rural	16 (66.7%)	15 (78.9%)	14 (70.0%)	
Urban	8 (33.3%)	4 (21.1%)	6 (30.0%)	
Average number of professionals	24.4 (12.2)	21.9 (11.1)	21.6 (9.84)	0.66
Average number of GPs	12.1 (6.11)	10.8 (5.49)	10.7 (5.03)	0.664

Average number of nurses	12.3 (6.14)	11.1 (5.63)	10.8 (4.87)	0.659
Average number of adult patients	16466 (9478)	14520 (9016)	14248 (8424)	0.671
Patients per GP	1327 (148)	1263 (211)	1247 (264)	0.405
Socioeconomic deprivation index (AQUAS)	52.8 (10.5)	49.4 (7.21)	52.4 (11.2)	0.497
Age of patients	44.6 (2.41)	44.9 (3.28)	45.6 (2.77)	0.5
% female patients	49.9 (0.94)	49.9 (1.10)	50.1 (1.20)	0.809
% immigrant patients	16.7 (6.86)	14.8 (7.96)	15.1 (6.03)	0.606
Synthetic quality-of-care indicator results				
Synthetic EQA indicator 2023	776 (76.4)	783 (60.4)	783 (78.5)	0.924
Synthetic EQA indicator 2024	706 (108)	719 (100)	710 (87.7)	0.911
Results of the quality-of-care indicators in the study				
Hypertension: Blood pressure control	67.8 (7.05)	68.4 (6.34)	68.6 (5.65)	0.909
Blood pressure control in diabetes	82.6 (3.22)	82.6 (2.15)	81.9 (4.13)	0.779
Blood pressure control in ischemic heart disease/cerebrovascular accident	73.1 (5.16)	73.4 (3.94)	72.6 (4.13)	0.851
Hypertension: Blood pressure control in patients with chronic kidney disease	85.5 (4.20)	84.7 (2.54)	85.4 (3.94)	0.787
Diagnostic adequacy of hypertension	71.0 (6.70)	69.4 (8.92)	70.4 (7.76)	0.792
Appropriate treatment of atrial fibrillation	93.3 (1.94)	92.7 (2.63)	93.8 (1.28)	0.215
Inhaler verification	76.7 (7.94)	79.5 (6.03)	78.1 (8.18)	0.466

Data sources and monitoring

Indicator results are obtained from SISAP, which extracts pseudo-anonymised EHR data weekly to calculate hundreds of indicator results, including those from the EQA. These data are routinely used for management purposes and will not require additional processing for this clinical trial. Data related to the participating professionals will be requested from ICS' Human Resources Department. Confidentiality will be guaranteed through encoding. Since the EQA is calculated based on PCP/professional codes, Human Resources will provide data using these codes, which are detached from personal identifiers. Subsequently, these codes will also undergo pseudo-anonymisation to ensure privacy.

Although the trial is designed to span the full year, the results of the seven indicators will be monitored weekly. Differences in the average indicator results among treatment arms will be calculated to assess the need for modifications

Retention and communication

A preparatory webinar, ongoing email support, territorial contact points, and end-of-study participation certificates are used to maximise retention.

Statistical analysis

Analyses will follow an intention-to-treat approach at the professional and PCP levels. Baseline balance is assessed using standardised mean differences. Primary analyses use linear mixed-effects models with fixed effects for intervention and imbalanced covariates, and random intercepts for clusters, reporting effects with 95% CIs. Additional pre-post analyses will be performed. Recording behaviour for blood pressure values will be compared across arms using descriptive statistics, t-tests, ANOVA/Tukey or non-parametric alternatives when assumptions are unmet. Analyses will be conducted in R 4.3.1.

Study conclusions

This study, finishing in December 2025, will generate robust evidence on how removing financial incentives and information feedback affects primary care quality, helping to distinguish the specific contribution of each mechanism. Despite limitations related to blinding and potential contamination, its prospective design, strong institutional support, and integration within an established quality-monitoring system ensure high relevance. The findings are expected to guide policymakers in optimising incentive schemes and inform quality-improvement strategies in Catalonia and other European health systems.

6. Study on GP incentives for diabetes prevention and management in Italy

Study background

This study constructs a matched patient–doctor dataset to evaluate financial incentive schemes in primary care in Italy for the period 2010-2017. It uses local operational agreements (*patti aziendali*) from the Province of Verona (Italy) to track institutional changes regarding the prevention and monitoring of diabetes. These agreements are established between GPs and LHUs to align clinical practice with regional priorities. The approach exploits a natural experiment and in particular the 2014 extension of the targeted population for improving the completeness of electronic health records (EHRs) of diabetic patients. Since 2014, the incentive scheme was designed in relation to the population aged 65 and above. This age-based eligibility criterion generated a staggered treatment introduction, as patients became eligible upon reaching age 65 at different points during the study period.

The paper examines five key outcomes among diabetic patients: quality of diagnostic documentation, GP visit frequency, glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) testing rates, testing intensity, and antidiabetic prescription patterns. We employ two complementary identification strategies to estimate causal effects: a staggered event study design that traces dynamic treatment effects over time, and a Difference-in-Discontinuities (DiD-C) approach that exploits the sharp age-65 eligibility threshold combined with temporal policy variation. Our results suggest that the introduction of incentives led to significant improvements in diabetes monitoring. Importantly, these quality improvements occurred without significantly increasing GP consultations or medication intensity, indicating efficient targeting of monitoring behaviours.

Incentive Design and Mechanism

The incentive scheme was structured as a capitation-based bonus of approximately €3 per patient.

This shift was operationalised through structured data collection protocols—often referred to as “patient summaries”—which required GPs to submit standardised clinical indicators such as HbA1c levels, blood pressure, lipid profiles, and medication records. These records had to be submitted to LHU administrative offices by the end of the year. The direct incentive rewarded GPs for updating EHRs of listed patients. Financial incentives were tied to the proportion of eligible

patients with complete electronic records, with minimum coverage thresholds ranging from 40% to 90%, depending on the LHU and year.

Given this institutional change, we hypothesise that the expansion of the incentivised population may have potentially led to measurable increases in diabetes diagnoses, more frequent visits and HbA1c monitoring, and a change in the volume of diabetes-related prescriptions per patient, reflecting improved disease management.

Other incentive schemes were also in place during the same period. These included programs to promote prescription of available generic drugs for hypertension (statins), to induce best-practices sharing within GPs' local teams, and to support GPs training and formation. Importantly, no other incentive scheme was targeting the prevention and monitoring of diabetes. The focus of this study is on the shift in the age threshold, from 75 to 65, introduced in 2014 for diabetic patients in the Province of Verona.

Hypotheses and aims

This study aims to evaluate whether financial incentives toward improvement and quality of digitalised clinical information in the primary care sector can effectively improve diabetes monitoring and care quality, without inducing unintended consequences such as excessive healthcare utilisation or inappropriate treatment intensification. We address three main research questions regarding the impact of pay-for-performance schemes on diabetes care in primary care settings. First, how do financial incentives affect patient monitoring, both regarding the extensive margin (the share of patients receiving at least one HbA1c test per year) and the intensive margin (the number of tests per patient)? Second, do such incentives improve diagnostic documentation quality and physician awareness of their diabetic patient population? Third, what are the spillover effects on broader healthcare utilisation, including GP consultations and medication prescriptions? By employing complementary identification strategies—a staggered event study exploiting temporal variation in policy implementation and a Difference-in-Discontinuities design leveraging the age-65 eligibility threshold—we aim to provide robust causal evidence on the effectiveness of financial incentives in shaping primary care physician behaviour and chronic disease management outcomes.

Methodology

Data source description

In order to quantitatively assess the impact of the financial incentives of interest on GPs' behaviours in the province of Verona, the data were obtained through

collaboration with the Italian Federation of General Medicine Doctors (FIMMG), which represents GPs operating in the country and serves them as a union. The dataset consists of administrative health records collected by the GPs who are affiliated FIMMG members across the three Local Health Units (*Unità Locali Socio Sanitarie*, LHUs): LHU 20 (Verona), LHU 21 (Legnago), and LHU 22 (Bussolengo). These data were anonymised and managed entirely by the FIMMG team. Due to the nature of the dataset, individual patient consent was not available. For this reason, the research team at the University of Verona did not directly manipulate any individual-level data.

The data include several key domains. Diagnoses are recorded using the ICD-9-CM classification, with a specific focus on chronic conditions. Prescription data are coded using the AIC system provided by the Italian Medicines Agency (AIFA), identifying drugs by active ingredient, package, and marketing authorisation holder. This coding system corresponds to the commercial name of the medications, and the dataset focuses on drugs reimbursed by the Italian National Health Service (NHS). Information on medical exams and procedures is also available, including not only the codes but also associated results and biomarkers. Finally, demographic and administrative information is available for each GP, including age, sex, and LHU assignment.

Sample definition

We restrict the analysis to patients aged 55–75 between 2010 and 2017. This age window ensures that the policy introduced in 2014, which targeted individuals aged 65 and above, can be evaluated against an internal control group of patients aged 55–64 who were not eligible. The inclusion of younger cohorts allows us to test for parallel trends prior to the intervention and to strengthen identification. Patients older than 75 are excluded to reduce attrition and selective drop-out.

Because the treatment is staggered, not all cohorts become eligible at the same time. In particular, individuals aged 55–64 in the early years of the panel serve as “not-yet-treated” cohorts, entering the treated group only after reaching the age threshold of 65. This staggered structure generates variation both across age groups and over time, which is exploited in the event study design.

The dataset is organised as follows. It contains yearly observations of patient cohorts aged 55-75 from 2010 to 2017 for 188 GPs operating in the 3 LHUs of the Province of Verona. Each cohort is uniquely identified by the patient's year of birth and their General Practitioner (GP). We exclude cohort-years falling outside these age and time intervals, resulting in an unbalanced panel. The core cohorts (birth years 1942–1955) are consistently observed across all eight years. In addition, edge

cohorts (born in 1941 and 1956) enter or exit the age window during the observation period, contributing a smaller number of partial observations. As a result, the regression sample is unbalanced, reflecting the inclusion of both full and partial cohorts within the age range. The final dataset comprises a total of 25,262 observations.

Outcomes and control variables

The empirical analysis is restricted to patients identified as diabetic through either “disease exemption”⁴ codes or antidiabetic medication use (ATC code A10). Within this population, we examine five key outcomes that capture different dimensions of diabetes care quality and intensity.

We consider the following outcome variables:

1. **Percentage of diagnosed diabetic patients:** The share of diabetic patients (identified through exemptions or medications) who also have a formal diabetes diagnosis recorded in the GP's clinical records. This measure captures diagnostic awareness and record-keeping quality, indicating whether GPs properly document and recognise which of their patients are diabetic. Improved alignment between exemptions/medications and clinical diagnoses suggests better diagnostic practices and increased physician awareness of their patient panel composition.
2. **Average number of GP visits:** The mean number of general practitioner consultations per diabetic patient in a given year. This captures the frequency of physician-patient interactions and monitoring effort among the diabetic population.
3. **Percentage checked for HbA1c:** The proportion of diabetic patients who received at least one glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) test during the year. This is a key quality indicator directly targeted by the pay-for-performance scheme, as regular HbA1c testing is essential for monitoring long-term glycaemic control⁵.
4. **Average number of HbA1c checks:** The mean number of HbA1c tests performed per diabetic patient. This measures the intensity of glycaemic monitoring beyond the binary indicator introduced in the previous point.
5. **Average number of antidiabetic prescriptions (A10):** The mean number of prescriptions for medications classified under ATC code A10 (drugs used in diabetes) per diabetic patient. This captures treatment intensity and pharmaceutical management of the disease.

To isolate the causal effect of financial incentives while accounting for potential confounding factors, all regression specifications include a comprehensive set of control variables. Patient-level controls capture the demographic and health composition of each GP's practice, including the share of female patients within

⁴ A disease exemption works as a waiver for patient co-payments.

⁵ The performance-based agreements did not include specific incentives for HbA1c testing. Although HbA1c was a required component of the diabetes dataset, financial incentives were tied to achieving coverage targets for the complete dataset among diabetic patients, rather than to individual parameters.

each cohort, the percentage of patients with low income (based on exemption codes⁶), the overall prevalence of patients diagnosed with diabetes in the cohort, and the average burden of comorbidities within the cohort measured through three ICD-9 condition categories: metabolic and endocrine disorders (codes 240-279), cardiovascular diseases (codes 390-459), and respiratory conditions (codes 460-519). GP-level controls include physician gender, year of birth, and the type of electronic health record software used in the practice. The inclusion of these time-varying patient characteristics and time-invariant GP attributes ensures that estimated treatment effects are not confounded by changes in patient mix or systematic differences across physicians. Additionally, all models include Local Health Unit (LHU) fixed effects to control for time-invariant local characteristics, year fixed effects to account for common temporal trends, and LHU-by-year interaction fixed effects to flexibly capture time-varying local shocks and policy changes that might differentially affect LHUs.

Identification strategy I: staggered event study

To identify the causal effect of the pay-for-performance scheme on diabetes care quality, we employ a staggered event study design using a fixed effects panel regression framework. This approach allows us to trace out the dynamic treatment effects over time, examining both pre-treatment trends and post-treatment evolution.

The estimated specification takes the form:

$$Y_{cit} = \sum_{(k \neq -1)} \beta_k \cdot D_{i,t+k} + X'_{cit} \gamma + Z'_i \delta + \alpha_i + \lambda_t + (\alpha_i \cdot \lambda_t) + \varepsilon_{cit}$$

where Y_{cit} represents the outcome for diabetic patients in cohort c assigned to general practitioner i in year t , and $D_{i,t+k}$ are event time indicators for k years before and after the policy implementation. The coefficients β_k capture the treatment effect at each relative time period, with $k = -1$ (one year before treatment) serving as the omitted reference category. This specification includes a rich set of controls. Time-varying patient cohorts' characteristics, X_{cit} , are the following: cohort age, shares of women in the cohort, shares of patients with low income proxied by the presence of an income-related exemption. For outcomes 2-5, we further control for the prevalence at the GP level of metabolic and endocrine disorders, cardiovascular and respiratory conditions. Time-invariant GP characteristics, Z_i , include GP's gender, birth year, and software used, LHU fixed effects α_i , year fixed effects λ_t . We also control for LHU-by-year fixed effects ($\alpha_i \cdot \lambda_t$) to account for time-varying local shocks and policy changes that might differentially affect local health units.

⁶ In addition to exemptions motivated by the fact of having a medical condition, exemptions are also granted to low-income individuals, irrespective of their health status.

Standard errors are clustered at the physician level to account for serial correlation within physician practices over time. The key identification assumption is that, in the absence of the policy change, outcomes would have evolved similarly across treatment cohorts—a parallel trends assumption that can be visually assessed by examining the estimated pre-treatment coefficients β_k for $k < -1$.

For the event-study specification, we further restrict the sample to cohorts that reach age 65 within the observation window. With data spanning 2010–2017, this corresponds to patients aged 58–75 in 2010 (i.e., born in 1952 or earlier). This restriction avoids the inclusion of “never-treated” cohorts—those who remain below the eligibility threshold throughout the observation period—which could otherwise distort the estimation of pre-treatment leads. Robustness checks are conducted on the broader 55–75 sample to confirm that results are stable when younger, not-yet-treated cohorts are included. The dataset, excluding the “never treated observations”, comprises a total of 22,328 observations.

Identification strategy II: difference in discontinuities (DiD-C)

To estimate the causal effect of financial incentives on retirement decisions, we employ a Difference-in-Discontinuities (DiD-C) approach that combines the strengths of regression discontinuity design and difference-in-differences methodology [50,51]. This method exploits both the sharp discontinuity in eligibility at age 65 and the temporal variation introduced by the policy change. Specifically, we compare the discontinuity in outcomes at the age threshold before the introduction of incentives (2010–2013) with the discontinuity after their implementation (2014–2017). The key advantage of this approach is that it differentiates out any pre-existing discontinuities at age 65 that are unrelated to the policy, such as eligibility for other age-based programs or behavioural changes naturally occurring at retirement age. The parameter of interest, θ , captures the change in the regression discontinuity effect attributable solely to the financial incentives. This identification strategy requires that, absent the policy change, the discontinuity at age 65 would have remained constant over time—a parallel trends assumption applied to the discontinuity itself. The estimated model takes the form:

$$Y_{cit} = \alpha + \tau \cdot 1\{\text{age}_{cit} \geq 65\} + \gamma \cdot 1\{\text{Post}_{cit}\} + \theta \cdot [1\{\text{age}_{cit} \geq 65\} \times 1\{\text{Post}_{cit}\}] + f(\text{age}_{cit}) + X'_{cit} \beta + Z'_i \delta + \alpha_i + \lambda_t + (\alpha_i \cdot \lambda_t) + \varepsilon_{it}$$

where τ represents the RD effect before incentives, $\tau + \theta$ represents the RD effect after incentives, and θ is the DiD-C estimate capturing the change in the RD effect due to the policy. We control for smooth functions of the running variable (age), individual fixed effects, time fixed effects, and their interactions to account for time-invariant individual heterogeneity and common time shocks, ensuring that the estimated effect reflects the causal impact of the incentive policy.

Results

The staggered event study results in **Table 1** and **Figure 1-5** reveal clear dynamic treatment effects of the pay-for-performance incentives on diabetes care quality. Examining the pre-treatment coefficients (t-4 through t-2), there are no statistically significant effects on the percentage of diagnosed patients or the number of GP visits, providing reassuring evidence in favour of the parallel trends assumption. However, there is a small pre-treatment dip in HbA1c monitoring at t-2 ($\beta = -0.044$, $p < 0.01$), though this reverses sharply upon policy implementation. This temporary decline could reflect anticipatory behaviour, where GPs may have delayed routine monitoring in expectation of the forthcoming incentive scheme, or simply random variation that was quickly corrected once the policy took effect. Importantly, the absence of a gradual upward trend in the pre-treatment period rules out concerns about anticipation effects driving the main results—GPs did not appear to strategically increase monitoring in advance of the policy. The isolated dip at t-2, followed by the immediate and substantial positive effect at t, suggests the policy implementation itself was the key driver of behavioural change rather than forward-looking adjustments. The key findings emerge in the post-treatment period: starting at t (the year of implementation), there is an immediate and significant increase in both the percentage of patients checked for HbA1c ($\beta = 0.074$, $p < 0.01$) and the average number of HbA1c checks per patient ($\beta = 0.110$, $p < 0.01$). These effects persist through t+1 and gradually attenuate by t+3, suggesting an initial strong response that stabilises over time. Interestingly, antidiabetic prescriptions show a marginally significant decline at t+1 and t+2 ($\beta \approx -0.28$ to -0.30 , $p < 0.10$), which may reflect improved disease management or substitution toward lifestyle interventions. The number of GP visits shows no significant change, indicating that improved monitoring did not come at the cost of increased consultation burden.

Figure 6-10 contain the regression discontinuity plots for the 5 outcomes over the 8 years of the study. Examining the discontinuities at age 65, where the incentive scheme eligibility begins, the plots reveal mixed evidence of treatment effects following the 2014 introduction of the incentive scheme. Specifically, there is no visible jump at the discontinuity for the share of patients with recorded diabetes diagnoses in electronic health records, suggesting that the financial incentives did not induce increased case identification at the eligibility threshold. Similarly, no clear jump is observed in the average number of GP visits or in the average number of antidiabetic medication prescriptions (A10), indicating that the scheme did not materially alter either the intensity of patient-physician contact or prescribing patterns for the targeted population aged 65 and over.

However, we do observe discontinuities in monitoring outcomes: the share of patients receiving glycated haemoglobin checks and the average number of HbA1c checks both show evidence of jumps at age 65 in the post-intervention period,

suggesting that the P4P scheme successfully incentivised increased adherence to recommended monitoring protocols, specifically at the point of eligibility. In particular, before the introduction of the pay-for-performance incentive (pre-2014 period), the age cohorts above and below the 65 threshold exhibited relatively comparable baseline levels of diabetes monitoring: among patients aged 60-64, 47.6% received at least one HbA1c measurement with an average of 0.83 tests per patient per year, while the cohort aged 65-69 showed modestly higher values at 50.6% coverage and 0.91 average tests. Following the implementation of the incentive scheme (post-2014 period), both groups demonstrated improvements in glycemic monitoring, yet the magnitude of change differed substantially between cohorts. The non-incentivized group aged 60-64 increased its coverage from 47.6% to 55.4%, representing a gain of 7.8 percentage points, while the average number of tests rose from 0.83 to 0.92, an increase of 0.09 tests per patient. In contrast, the incentivized cohort aged 65-69 experienced markedly larger improvements, with coverage rising from 50.6% to 67.3%, a gain of 16.7 percentage points, and the average number of tests increasing from 0.91 to 1.11, representing an additional 0.20 tests per patient. The difference-in-differences estimates therefore amount to approximately 8.9 percentage points for patient coverage and 0.11 tests for monitoring intensity, suggesting that the financial incentive produced meaningful additional improvements in diabetes care quality beyond the secular trend observed in the younger, non-incentivized population.

This pattern indicates that while the incentive scheme did not affect diagnosis rates, care utilisation, or prescribing behaviour, it did influence the quality of diabetes management through enhanced biochemical monitoring, which represents a key intermediate outcome in preventing long-term diabetic complications. To further investigate these findings and establish causal estimates while accounting for potential confounders, we employ a difference-in-discontinuities framework that controls for both time-varying and time-invariant patient cohort characteristics as well as GP-level controls.

The Difference-in-Discontinuities (DiD-C) results in **Table 2-6** corroborate and strengthen the findings previously obtained with the staggered event-study framework by isolating the causal effect of incentives from other age-related discontinuities at 65. Before the policy (2010-2013), there were no significant discontinuities at the age threshold for any outcome, with RDD coefficients close to zero and statistically insignificant. After the policy implementation (2014-2017), sharp positive discontinuities emerge for key quality indicators: the percentage of diagnosed patients increases by 4.7 percentage points ($p < 0.05$), the share receiving HbA1c checks jumps by 13.3 percentage points ($p < 0.01$), and the average number of glycemic checks increases by 0.218 units. The DiD-C estimates—capturing the change in discontinuity attributable solely to the incentives—confirm statistically significant effects for HbA1c monitoring ($\theta = 0.144$, $p < 0.01$ for share

checked; $\theta = 0.265$, $p < 0.05$ for number of checks). While the effects on diagnosis rates and prescription intensity show positive point estimates, they remain statistically insignificant, suggesting that the policy's primary impact was on monitoring intensity rather than treatment patterns. Across both specifications, we control for patient demographics, comorbidity profiles, socioeconomic characteristics, GP characteristics, and a comprehensive set of fixed effects, including LHU-by-year interactions to account for regional time-varying shocks.

Table 1: staggered event study results

	(1) % of diagnose d	(2) Avg visits	(3) % checked for HbA1c	(4) Avg HbA1c checks	(5) Avg A10 prescr.
Controls					
t-4	-0.003 (0.015)	0.008 (0.404)	-0.031 (0.020)	-0.064 (0.044)	-0.080 (0.160)
t-3	-0.009 (0.012)	0.554* (0.330)	-0.014 (0.017)	-0.023 (0.035)	-0.117 (0.139)
t-2	-0.007 (0.008)	0.087 (0.248)	-0.044*** (0.016)	-0.083** (0.033)	-0.154 (0.126)
t	0.009 (0.009)	0.189 (0.272)	0.074*** (0.020)	0.110*** (0.037)	-0.106 (0.112)
t+1	0.009 (0.010)	0.089 (0.354)	0.082*** (0.019)	0.088** (0.036)	-0.280* (0.153)
t+2	0.007 (0.012)	-0.281 (0.393)	0.040** (0.018)	0.056 (0.039)	-0.295* (0.174)
t+3	-0.006 (0.012)	-0.491 (0.410)	0.005 (0.020)	0.025 (0.043)	-0.250 (0.188)
Share of women	0.032 (0.041)	0.061 (1.203)	0.015 (0.032)	0.042 (0.071)	-0.574 (0.486)
% of 65+ patients with low income	0.078 (0.049)	2.909*** (1.000)	-0.005 (0.030)	0.052 (0.065)	0.328 (0.344)
% of patients with very low income	0.049 (0.033)	-1.374* (0.825)	0.042 (0.042)	0.070 (0.090)	0.000 (0.341)
% of diabetic (exemption or medication)		-5.160*** (1.950)	-0.257*** (0.055)	-0.549*** (0.128)	-7.925*** (0.794)

Avg ICD-9 240-279 conditions		8.359*** (1.373)	0.275*** (0.046)	0.514*** (0.101)	3.491*** (0.467)
Avg ICD-9 390-459 conditions		9.985*** (1.299)	0.370*** (0.043)	0.691*** (0.088)	3.247*** (0.541)
Avg ICD-9 460-519 conditions		0.944 (1.188)	-0.032 (0.043)	-0.058 (0.089)	0.157 (0.445)
Female GP		0.842 (0.703)	0.016 (0.026)	0.022 (0.054)	0.907*** (0.250)
Constant	0.317*** (0.110)	-5.469*** (1.658)	0.487*** (0.099)	0.776*** (0.213)	4.069*** (0.864)

GPs' birth year	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
GPs' gender	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
GPs' software	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
LHU FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
LHU x Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Observations	22,328	22,328	22,328	22,328	22,328
Clusters	188	188	188	188	188
Within R2	0.155	0.134	0.115	0.062	0.095
Between R2	0.094	0.529	0.269	0.207	0.091
Overall R2	0.113	0.476	0.208	0.148	0.091

Standard errors in parentheses

* p<0.10, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.01

Figure 1: event-study plot, % diagnosed

Figure 2: event-study plot, Average number of visits

Figure 3: event-study plot, % of patients checked for HbA1c

Figure 4: event-study plot, average number of HbA1c checks

Figure 5: event-study plot, average number of antidiabetic prescriptions (ATC2 code: A10)

Figure 6: Share of patients within a cohort with a diabetes diagnosis reported in their EHR

Figure 7: Number of GP visits among diabetic patients

Figure 8: share with glycaemic checks among diabetic patients

Figure 9: Average number of glycated haemoglobin checks among diabetic patients

Figure 10: Average number of A10 prescriptions among diabetic patients

Table 2: DiD-C results, diagnoses

% of diabetic patients	(1) Incentives off (2010-2013)	(2) Incentives on: 2014-2017	(3) DiD-C
Conventional RDD coefficient	-0.004 (0.028)	0.047** (-0.02)	0.052 (0.034)
N	12,300	12,962	
Optimal BW	5.581	4.655	
% of female patients	Yes	Yes	Yes
GP's gender	Yes	Yes	Yes
GP's software FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
GP's year of birth FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
ULSS FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year x LHU FE	Yes	Yes	Yes

This table presents Difference-in-Discontinuities estimates of the causal effect of the incentives on the share of patients within a cohort with a diabetes diagnosis reported in their electronic health records. Column (1) reports the conventional RDD coefficient for the pre-policy period (2010–2013), measuring any pre-existing discontinuity at age 65 unrelated to financial incentives. Column (2) presents the RDD coefficient for the post-policy period (2014–2017), capturing the overall discontinuity after incentive implementation. Column (3) displays the DiD-C estimate (θ), which is the difference between columns (2) and (1), representing the change in the discontinuity attributable solely to the pay-for-performance scheme. This is the causal parameter of interest.

The estimation uses local linear regression with optimal bandwidth selection following [52]. The running variable is patient age centred at 65. All specifications control for the share of female patients in the GP's practice, GP gender, GP software used, GP year of birth, the percentage of patients with diabetes, the prevalence of patients with metabolic disorders (ICD-9 codes 240-279), cardiovascular conditions (ICD-9 codes 390-459), respiratory diseases (ICD-9 codes 460-519), and the share of low-income patients. We include year fixed effects, Local Health Unit (LHU) fixed effects, and their interactions to account for time-varying regional shocks. Standard errors are reported in parentheses. Statistical significance is denoted as * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Table 3: DiD-C results, GP visits among diabetic patients

Number of visits	(1) Incentives off (2010-2013)	(2) Incentives on: 2014-2017	(3) DiD-C
Conventional RDD coefficient	-0.259 (0.604)	0.430 (0.588)	0.689 (0.844)
N	12,300	12,962	
Optimal BW	3.441	3.449	
% of female patients	Yes	Yes	Yes
GP's gender	Yes	Yes	Yes
GP's software FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
GP's year of birth FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
% with diabetes	Yes	Yes	Yes
% with ICD-9 codes 240-279	Yes	Yes	Yes
% with ICD-9 codes 390-459	Yes	Yes	Yes
% with ICD-9 codes 460-519	Yes	Yes	Yes
% with low income	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
ULSS FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year x LHU FE	Yes	Yes	Yes

This table presents Difference-in-Discontinuities estimates of the causal effect of the incentives on the number of GP visits among diabetic patients. Column (1) reports the conventional RDD coefficient for the pre-policy period (2010–2013), measuring any pre-existing discontinuity at age 65 unrelated to financial incentives. Column (2) presents the RDD coefficient for the post-policy period (2014–2017), capturing the overall discontinuity after incentive implementation. Column (3) displays the DiD-C estimate (θ), which is the difference between columns (2) and (1), representing the change in the discontinuity attributable solely to the pay-for-performance scheme. This is the causal parameter of interest.

The estimation uses local linear regression with optimal bandwidth selection following [52]. The running variable is patient age centred at 65. All specifications control for the share of female patients in the GP's practice, GP gender, GP software used, GP year of birth, the percentage of patients with diabetes, the prevalence of patients with metabolic disorders (ICD-9 codes 240-279), cardiovascular conditions (ICD-9 codes 390-459), respiratory diseases (ICD-9 codes 460-519), and the share of low-income patients. We include year fixed effects, Local Health Unit (LHU) fixed effects, and their interactions to account for time-varying regional shocks. Standard errors are reported in parentheses. Statistical significance is denoted as * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Table 4: DiD-C results, % of patients checked for HbA1c

Share with HbA1c check	(1) Incentives off (2010-2013)	(2) Incentives on: 2014-2017	(3) DiD-C
Conventional RDD coefficient	-0.011 (0.035)	0.133*** (0.035)	0.144*** (0.049)
N	12,300	12,962	
Optimal BW	3.007	2.968	
% of female patients	Yes	Yes	Yes
GP's gender	Yes	Yes	Yes
% with diabetes	Yes	Yes	Yes
% with ICD-9 codes 240-279	Yes	Yes	Yes
% with ICD-9 codes 390-459	Yes	Yes	Yes
% with ICD-9 codes 460-519	Yes	Yes	Yes
% with low income	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
GP's year of birth FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
ULSS FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Software FE	Yes	Yes	Yes

This table presents Difference-in-Discontinuities estimates of the causal effect of the incentives on the share of patients with a glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) check.

Column (1) reports the conventional RDD coefficient for the pre-policy period (2010–2013), measuring any pre-existing discontinuity at age 65 unrelated to financial incentives. Column (2) presents the RDD coefficient for the post-policy period (2014–2017), capturing the overall discontinuity after incentive implementation. Column (3) displays the DiD-C estimate (θ), which is the difference between columns (2) and (1), representing the change in the discontinuity attributable solely to the pay-for-performance scheme. This is the causal parameter of interest.

The estimation uses local linear regression with optimal bandwidth selection following [52]. The running variable is patient age centred at 65. All specifications control for the share of female patients in the GP's practice, GP gender, GP software used, GP year of birth, the percentage of patients with diabetes, the prevalence of patients with metabolic disorders (ICD-9 codes 240-279), cardiovascular conditions (ICD-9 codes 390-459), respiratory diseases (ICD-9 codes 460-519), and the share of low-income patients. We include year fixed effects, Local Health Unit (LHU) fixed effects, and their interactions to account for time-varying regional shocks. Standard errors are reported in parentheses. Statistical significance is denoted as * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Table 5: DiD-C results, average number of glycated haemoglobin checks among diabetic patients

Number of HbA1c checks	(1) Incentives off (2010-2013)	(2) Incentives on: 2014-2017	(3) DiD-C
Conventional RDD coefficient	-0.046 (0.084)	0.218*** (0.060)	0.265** (0.103)
N	12,300	12,962	
Optimal BW	3.007	2.968	
% of female patients	Yes	Yes	Yes
GP's gender	Yes	Yes	Yes
% with diabetes	Yes	Yes	Yes
% with ICD-9 codes 240-279	Yes	Yes	Yes
% with ICD-9 codes 390-459	Yes	Yes	Yes
% with ICD-9 codes 460-519	Yes	Yes	Yes
% with low income	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
GP's year of birth FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
ULSS FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Software FE	Yes	Yes	Yes

This table presents Difference-in-Discontinuities estimates of the causal effect of the incentives on the average number of glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) checks among diabetic patients. Column (1) reports the conventional RDD coefficient for the pre-policy period (2010–2013), measuring any pre-existing discontinuity at age 65 unrelated to financial incentives. Column (2) presents the RDD coefficient for the post-policy period (2014–2017), capturing the overall discontinuity after incentive implementation. Column (3) displays the DiD-C estimate (θ), which is the difference between columns (2) and (1), representing the change in the discontinuity attributable solely to the pay-for-performance scheme. This is the causal parameter of interest.

The estimation uses local linear regression with optimal bandwidth selection following [52]. The running variable is patient age centred at 65. All specifications control for the share of female patients in the GP's practice, GP gender, GP software used, GP year of birth, the percentage of patients with diabetes, the prevalence of patients with metabolic disorders (ICD-9 codes 240-279), cardiovascular conditions (ICD-9 codes 390-459), respiratory diseases (ICD-9 codes 460-519), and the share of low-income patients. We include year fixed effects, Local Health Unit (LHU) fixed effects, and their interactions to account for time-varying regional shocks. Standard errors are reported in parentheses. Statistical significance is denoted as * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Table 6: DiD-C results, average number of A10 prescriptions among diabetic patients

Number of A10 prescriptions	(1)	(2)	(3)
	Incentives off (2010-2013)	Incentives on: 2014-2017	DiD-C
Conventional RDD coefficient	-0.252 (0.338)	-0.008 (0.327)	0.244 (0.470)
N	12,300	12,962	
Optimal BW	3.007	2.968	
% of female patients	Yes	Yes	Yes
GP's gender	Yes	Yes	Yes
% with diabetes	Yes	Yes	Yes
% with ICD-9 codes 240-279	Yes	Yes	Yes
% with ICD-9 codes 390-459	Yes	Yes	Yes
% with ICD-9 codes 460-519	Yes	Yes	Yes
% with low income	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
GP's year of birth FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
ULSS FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Software FE	Yes	Yes	Yes

This table presents Difference-in-Discontinuities estimates of the causal effect of the incentives on the average number of antidiabetic prescriptions among diabetic patients. Column (1) reports the conventional RDD coefficient for the pre-policy period (2010–2013), measuring any pre-existing discontinuity at age 65 unrelated to financial incentives. Column (2) presents the RDD coefficient for the post-policy period (2014–2017), capturing the overall discontinuity after incentive implementation. Column (3) displays the DiD-C estimate (θ), which is the difference between columns (2) and (1), representing the change in the discontinuity attributable solely to the pay-for-performance scheme. This is the causal parameter of interest.

The estimation uses local linear regression with optimal bandwidth selection following [52]. The running variable is patient age centred at 65. All specifications control for the share of female patients in the GP's practice, GP gender, GP software used, GP year of birth, the percentage of patients with diabetes, the prevalence of patients with metabolic disorders (ICD-9 codes 240-279), cardiovascular conditions (ICD-9 codes 390-459), respiratory diseases (ICD-9 codes 460-519), and the share of low-income patients. We include year fixed effects, Local Health Unit (LHU) fixed effects, and their interactions to account for time-varying regional shocks. Standard errors are reported in parentheses. Statistical significance is denoted as * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Study limitations

Several limitations warrant acknowledgement. First, our study period extends only through 2017, limiting our ability to assess long-term effects. Whether the observed monitoring improvements represent permanent shifts in practice patterns or temporary responses that fade as financial incentives become routine remains an open question. Second, our current analysis focuses exclusively on patients already identified as diabetic through pharmaceutical treatment or disease exemptions, precluding examination of whether the incentive scheme altered diagnostic practices or case identification patterns. Third, our analysis relies on process quality indicators available in administrative claims data, which precludes the examination of clinical outcomes, such as glycemic control levels, complication rates, or patient-reported health status. Fourth, the external validity of our findings to other healthcare systems—particularly those with stronger market competition, different physician payment models, or alternative patient populations—requires careful consideration given the specific institutional features of Italy's National Health Service.

Study conclusions

This paper provides robust causal evidence that even incentives targeting the completeness of electronic records can significantly improve the quality of chronic disease monitoring in primary care settings. Leveraging the 2014 introduction of diabetes monitoring incentives in the Province of Verona, we employ complementary identification strategies—staggered event studies and difference-in-discontinuities—to isolate the causal impact of financial incentives on diabetes care processes among patients with documented diagnoses (identified through pharmaceutical treatment or disease-specific exemptions).

Our findings reveal a clear pattern: administrative incentives, even those modest in magnitude and requiring minimal bureaucratic effort, can substantially improve adherence to evidence-based monitoring protocols. Following policy implementation, we document immediate and statistically significant increases in both the share of patients receiving glycosylated haemoglobin testing and monitoring intensity within the diagnosed diabetic population. These effects emerge precisely when and where incentives are applied—at policy implementation and at the age 65 eligibility threshold—with no evidence of pre-treatment trends threatening causal interpretation.

Critically, the policy impact was concentrated exclusively on incentivised monitoring activities, with no evidence of effects on broader care dimensions. GP consultations and antidiabetic prescriptions remained unchanged, indicating that improved monitoring did not impose additional burden or alter treatment patterns among diagnosed patients. This precise targeting suggests the administrative

incentive operated as intended, focusing physician attention on specific quality metrics without distorting overall care delivery for established diabetic patients. These findings carry important policy implications. They demonstrate that process-based incentives can successfully modify clinical practice patterns in environments such as the Italian context, which features publicly contracted GPs with fixed patient panels and salary-based compensation. This suggests appropriately designed administrative incentives can complement rather than crowd out intrinsic professional motivation.

From a policy perspective, our findings suggest that modest financial incentives tied to administrative documentation can generate meaningful process improvements.

7. Discussion

Across three complementary studies performed with data from the Catalan public primary care system, this work package provides robust evidence on how information provision and financial incentives shape quality-of-care performance in primary care. Longitudinal analyses from 2010–2019 showed that both informing professionals through a unified online platform and economic incentivisation contributed substantially to improving newly created indicators and reducing unwarranted variation between practices. Although incentivisation did not consistently outperform information alone, the combination of both interventions supported significant improvements in most new indicators, reinforcing the importance of transparent, routinely updated feedback systems. These findings also highlighted the limited responsiveness of derived indicators, likely due to spillover from their source measures. This emphasised the need for careful indicator selection and the avoidance of redundancy in quality frameworks.

This evidence was strengthened by a second study evaluating recovery from the COVID-19 system shock. Using more than five years of monthly data across 287 PCPs, the staggered reintroduction of incentives provided a natural experiment for assessing the role of financial and informational levers under exceptional circumstances. Early reinstatement of incentives significantly accelerated recovery, with a two-fold higher likelihood of returning to pre-pandemic performance, while information alone also supported gradual improvement. Recovery patterns varied by indicator type and practice context, with rural and smaller practices showing greater resilience. These findings validate the complementary value of financial and non-financial strategies and illustrate that adaptability and targeted design are crucial when health systems face acute disruptions.

The third ongoing study builds directly on these insights by prospectively testing the consequences of removing financial incentives and information from selected indicators. This experimental design will help disentangle the specific contribution of each mechanism—an evidence gap identified in both retrospective and pandemic-related analyses. By examining quality drops after removing incentives alone versus removing both incentives and feedback, the trial will clarify whether information can sustain quality in the absence of financial rewards, and under what conditions and for which clinical activities performance may deteriorate. Together, the three studies establish a coherent, policy-relevant evidence base: informing professionals is an effective, scalable, and cost-efficient strategy; financial incentives have additional value in accelerating improvement or recovery for selected indicators; and the optimal design of quality-improvement schemes requires careful targeting, continuous monitoring, and alignment with clinical relevance and contextual needs.

The information and the pure incentive mechanisms are even more narrowly related in the setting that was studied for the Italian setting. In this case, GPs became eligible for financial incentives conditional on improving to a certain extent the quality of the electronic records of their patients. The results from the two alternative analyses conducted – a difference-in-Differences event study and a Difference-in-Discontinuities (DiD-C) approach consistently suggest that the introduction of incentives led to significant improvements in diabetes monitoring. These quality improvements occurred without significantly increasing GP consultations or medication intensity.

8. Conclusions

- **Information provision is a powerful and cost-effective quality-improvement tool**, consistently associated with improved indicator performance and reduced variation across practices.
- **Financial incentives add value for selected indicators**, particularly those with low baseline performance or in contexts requiring accelerated improvement (e.g., post-COVID-19 recovery).
- **The impact of interventions varies by indicator type and context**: newly created indicators respond more strongly, derived measures show weaker effects, rural/smaller practices tend to respond to recovery incentives faster than urban/larger ones, and intervention effects also depend on the type of clinical activity targeted.
- **Indicator design matters**: avoiding redundant or closely related indicators reduces spillover effects, and this could enhance intervention impacts.
- **The study on incentive and information removal will provide critical causal evidence**, clarifying whether information alone can sustain quality and identifying risks of performance decline when financial incentives are withdrawn.
- For policymakers, **combining targeted incentives with continuous information feedback is likely the most effective strategy**, enabling both sustained quality in routine periods and rapid recovery after system shocks.
- **Future quality-improvement schemes** should be more **selective**, focusing **financial incentives** on **high-value indicators** while ensuring **transparent quality-of-care data for all measures**.
- Providing **incentives to improve the quality of electronic recording** of chronic patient data can **enhance disease monitoring** without increasing GPs workload

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Annex 1 – Supplementary material from the study on the impact of introducing financial incentives and information provision in Catalonia (Spain)

Annex Table 1.1 | Interrupted time series (ITS) analysis on average indicator results among ICS primary care practices for the 39 quality-of-care indicators introduced as informed or incentivised after 2013.

Indicator	Derived	Scheme change	Year of intervention	Baseline result (%) [†]	Trend before scheme change (% pt change) (95% CI)	Step change (% pt change) (95% CI)	Change in trend (additional % pt change) (95% CI)	End result (%) [‡]
Reduction of alcohol consumption in high-risk drinkers	New	Introduced as Incentivised	2014	21.67	1.39 (0.29 to 2.48)*	19.67 (11.34 to 27.99)*	-0.7 (-3.14 to 1.74)	46.58
Correct treatment of asymptomatic hyperuricemia			2014	68.64	0.85 (0.51 to 1.18)*	19.66 (16.6 to 22.72)*	0.25 (-0.66 to 1.16)	95.75
Adequacy of treatment for acute bronchitis, acute rhinopharyngitis, and influenza			2014	77.73	-0.15 (-0.6 to 0.3)	2.36 (0.74 to 3.98)*	1.09 (0.52 to 1.65)*	84.52
Inadequate prevention of gastropathy with PPIs [†]			2014	54.66	-0.31 (-0.43 to -0.18)*	-1.48 (-2.5 to -0.47)*	-1.09 (-1.36 to -0.83)*	45.23
Low cardiovascular risk with poorly indicated lipid-lowering agents [†]			2014	7.55	-0.25 (-0.33 to -0.18)*	-1.07 (-1.55 to -0.6)*	-0.34 (-0.48 to -0.2)*	2.72
Weight reduction in obese and overweight patients			2014	35.8	-0.06 (-0.83 to 0.71)	-2.86 (-5.42 to -0.31)*	0.89 (0.09 to 1.68)*	37.29
Treatment adequacy in acute tonsillitis			2015	78	0.73 (0.48 to 0.97)*	-0.85 (-1.78 to 0.08)	-0.27 (-0.64 to 0.11)	83.45
Adequacy of treatment in acute gastroenteritis			2014	97.15	-0.08 (-0.25 to 0.09)	-0.07 (-0.73 to 0.59)	0.16 (-0.02 to 0.34)	97.31
Adult triple viral vaccination			2014	18.49	1.98 (1.9 to 2.06)*	0.1 (-0.48 to 0.68)	-0.78 (-0.94 to -0.62)*	32.39
Good control of anticoagulant treatment			2014	91	0.85 (0.44 to 1.26)*	-2.12 (-3.68 to -0.57)*	-0.62 (-1.18 to -0.06)*	94.35
Incorrect use of PSA in individuals older than 70 [†]		2018	20.2	-1.4 (-1.64 to -1.16)*	-0.56 (-1.63 to 0.51)	1.21 (0.97 to 1.45)*	10.25	
Diagnostic adequacy of hypercholesterolemia		Informed to Incentivised	2015	62.4	2.31 (0.82 to 3.8)*	8.37 (-3.22 to 19.96)	-0.15 (-2.59 to 2.3)	85.3
Diagnostic adequacy of hypertension			2015	46.58	4.61 (4.37 to 4.86)*	5.19 (-4.9 to 15.29)	-1.4 (-3.68 to 0.89)	74.87
Diagnostic adequacy of cardiovascular disease	2015		40.14	12.74 (11.64 to 13.85)*	-2.69 (-12.01 to 6.62)	-8.93 (-10.94 to -6.92)*	78.44	

Diagnostic adequacy of obesity			2015	71.66	5.32 (4.67 to 5.96)*	2.45 (-3.82 to 8.73)	-3.24 (-4.61 to -1.88)*	93.53	
Diagnostic adequacy of other health problems			2015	76.54	3.99 (1.86 to 6.11)*	-2.01 (-8.17 to 4.15)	-2.81 (-3.55 to -2.07)*	87.36	
Diagnostic adequacy of respiratory disease			2015	63.65	6.3 (6.13 to 6.46)*	-2.94 (-6.26 to 0.38)	-5.36 (-6.05 to -4.66)*	77.37	
Diagnostic quality of T2DM			2015	95.13	0.73 (0.46 to 0.99)*	0.1 (-0.71 to 0.9)	-0.67 (-0.77 to -0.57)*	96.99	
Diagnostic adequacy of cardiovascular disease		Introduced as Informed	2013	13.53	6.08 (4.98 to 7.18)*	8.87 (6.32 to 11.41)*	6.66 (5.56 to 7.77)*	52.88	
Diagnostic adequacy of hypertension			2013	43.94	-1.09 (-1.33 to -0.85)*	6.02 (5.46 to 6.58)*	5.7 (5.46 to 5.95)*	51.19	
Diagnostic adequacy of obesity			2013	55.25	3.37 (2.73 to 4.01)*	6.59 (5.11 to 8.07)*	1.95 (1.31 to 2.59)*	76.98	
Diagnostic adequacy of respiratory disease			2013	50.96	3.12 (2.95 to 3.28)*	3.41 (3.03 to 3.79)*	3.18 (3.01 to 3.34)*	69.94	
Annual ECG in AF risk population			2017	75.85	-3.55 (-5.44 to -1.66)*	8.05 (-2.15 to 18.25)	5.53 (3.6 to 7.45)*	64.92	
Patients with excessive control of T2DM†			2017	41.42	1.08 (0.6 to 1.57)*	-2.15 (-4.65 to 0.36)	-1.25 (-1.74 to -0.77)*	46.2	
Diagnostic adequacy of hypercholesterolemia			2013	55.98	1.51 (0.02 to 3)*	1.21 (-2.23 to 4.65)	0.81 (-0.68 to 2.3)	64.71	
Diagnostic adequacy of other health problems			2013	58.27	5.67 (3.54 to 7.8)*	0.28 (-4.63 to 5.2)	-1.69 (-3.81 to 0.44)	80.53	
Diagnostic quality of T2DM			2013	92.71	0.85 (0.59 to 1.11)*	-0.24 (-0.84 to 0.36)	-0.12 (-0.38 to 0.14)	95.85	
T2DM: Screening for albuminuria			2017	53.69	2.37 (1.11 to 3.63)*	-2.92 (-7.02 to 1.18)	-1.22 (-2.54 to 0.09)	73.37	
Antiplatelet therapy in T2DM without cardiovascular disease†			2017	26.24	-1.54 (-1.68 to -1.4)*	2.51 (1.74 to 3.28)*	0.24 (0.09 to 0.38)*	15.25	
Biennial heart rate measurement in individuals aged 60 or older			2017	63.77	1.39 (0.81 to 1.98)*	-2.38 (-5.05 to 0.3)	-2.09 (-2.7 to -1.48)*	71.25	
LDL control in patients with high cardiovascular risk	Derived		Introduced as Incentivised	2014	59.23	1.27 (0.66 to 1.89)*	5.03 (1.95 to 8.11)*	-1.2 (-2.27 to -0.14)*	69.04
Blood pressure control in diabetes				2014	72.14	1.74 (1.25 to 2.22)*	0.02 (-2.23 to 2.26)	-1.22 (-1.8 to -0.64)*	81.45
Blood pressure control in ischemic cardiopathy/cerebrovascular accident		2014		56.31	3.44 (2.82 to 4.05)*	-1.11 (-3.46 to 1.23)	-2.47 (-3.17 to -1.78)*	73.31	

Good control of hypothyroidism			2014	54.28	3.95 (3.3 to 4.61)*	1.37 (-0.81 to 3.54)	-2.85 (-3.65 to -2.05)*	72.71
ACE inhibitor treatment in T2DM with microalbuminuria	Introduced as Informed		2017	78.39	0.09 (-0.26 to 0.45)	1.67 (0.28 to 3.06)*	-1.13 (-1.6 to -0.66)*	77.82
Weight reduction in overweight and obese diabetic patients			2017	30.72	-0.79 (-1.11 to -0.48)*	2.22 (0.8 to 3.64)*	0.87 (0.52 to 1.22)*	28.1
Smoking cessation in T2DM			2018	17.81	-0.88 (-1.31 to -0.45)*	-0.68 (-3.55 to 2.19)	1.31 (0.88 to 1.74)*	10.47
LDL measurement in secondary prevention			2018	65.08	0.81 (0.03 to 1.59)*	-2 (-5 to 1.01)	-0.07 (-0.84 to 0.71)	73.23
Blood pressure measurement in cardiovascular disease			2018	77.07	0.68 (0.12 to 1.24)*	-3.63 (-6.56 to -0.69)*	-0.19 (-0.75 to 0.37)	80.14
Blood pressure measurement in T2DM			2017	83.06	0.74 (0.55 to 0.92)*	-2.51 (-3.09 to -1.93)*	-0.51 (-0.87 to -0.16)*	86.26
BMI measurement			2017	59.71	2.57 (1.88 to 3.25)*	-4.28 (-6.59 to -1.96)*	-1.99 (-2.7 to -1.29)*	72.82
HbA1c measurement			2017	77	0.98 (0.61 to 1.35)*	-2.17 (-3.41 to -0.94)*	-0.4 (-0.8 to -0.005)*	84.07
LDL control in T2DM with high cardiovascular risk			2017	70.85	1.68 (1.38 to 1.99)*	-3.24 (-4.5 to -1.98)*	-2.14 (-2.75 to -1.52)*	78.71
LDL control in T2DM with ischemic cardiopathy/cerebrovascular accident			2017	63.14	1.94 (1.41 to 2.47)*	-3.83 (-5.5 to -2.16)*	-0.85 (-1.38 to -0.31)*	76.73
Physical activity in T2DM: sedentary individuals improving in the change stage			2017	25.51	6.58 (5.21 to 7.95)*	-3.8 (-10.27 to 2.67)	-9.09 (-12.68 to -5.5)*	56.64
Tobacco abstinence in T2DM			2017	81.68	-0.14 (-0.3 to 0.01)	-1.02 (-1.71 to -0.33)*	-0.14 (-0.47 to 0.19)	79.65

† Inverse indicators (negative step and trend changes represent improvement); ‡ Introduced as Incentivised: baseline result 2010, end result 2019; Informed to Incentivised: baseline result 2013, end result 2019; Introduced as Informed: baseline result 2010, end result 2019 (except for diagnostic indicators, 2014); all derived indicators: baseline result 2010, end result 2019; * Coefficient different than zero with p<0.05; **bold text** indicates positive impacts.

Annex Table 1.2 | Interrupted time series (ITS) analysis on the coefficient of variation (CV) among ICS primary care practices for the 39 quality-of-care indicators introduced as informed or incentivised since 2013.

Indicator	Derived	Scheme change	Year of intervention	Baseline result (%) [‡]	Trend before scheme change (annual CV change) (95% CI)	Step change (CV change) (95% CI)	Change in trend (additional CV change) (95% CI)	End result (%) [‡]
Reduction of alcohol consumption in high-risk drinkers	New	Introduced as Incentivised	2014	0.52	-0.06 (-0.09 to -0.03)*	-0.14 (-0.24 to -0.04)*	0.06 (0.03 to 0.09)*	0.16
Correct treatment of asymptomatic hyperuricemia			2014	0.17	-0.01 (-0.01 to -0.004)*	-0.11 (-0.12 to -0.09)*	0.001 (-0.003 to 0.005)	0.02
Adequacy of treatment for acute bronchitis, acute rhinopharyngitis, and influenza			2014	0.09	-0.004 (-0.005 to -0.003)*	-0.01 (-0.01 to -0.001)*	-1e-04 (-0.002 to 0.002)	0.05
Weight reduction in obese and overweight patients			2014	0.14	-0.004 (-0.01 to -7e-04)*	-0.01 (-0.03 to -0.003)*	0.002 (-0.001 to 0.005)	0.1
Incorrect use of PSA in individuals older than 70			2018	0.33	0.01 (0.01 to 0.01)*	-0.02 (-0.04 to 0.004)	-0.03 (-0.04 to -0.03)*	0.36
Adequacy of treatment in acute gastroenteritis			2014	0.02	-1e-04 (-0.002 to 0.001)	-0.003 (-0.01 to 0.003)	-4e-04 (-0.002 to 0.001)	0.01
Low cardiovascular risk with poorly indicated lipid-lowering agents			2014	0.32	0.004 (0.002 to 0.01)*	0.01 (-0.01 to 0.02)	-0.003 (-0.01 to 0.004)	0.33
Adult triple viral vaccination			2014	0.39	-0.03 (-0.03 to -0.02)*	0.005 (-0.01 to 0.01)	0.01 (0.01 to 0.02)*	0.24
Good control of anticoagulant treatment			2014	0.09	-0.02 (-0.03 to -0.01)*	0.03 (-0.01 to 0.06)	0.02 (0.005 to 0.03)*	0.03
Inadequate prevention of gastropathy with PPIs			2014	0.07	0.002 (0.001 to 0.003)*	-0.001 (-0.01 to 0.004)	0.01 (0.01 to 0.01)*	0.12
Treatment adequacy in acute tonsillitis			2015	0.1	-0.005 (-0.01 to -0.003)*	0.002 (-0.01 to 0.01)	0.01 (0.005 to 0.01)*	0.09
Diagnostic adequacy of cardiovascular disease		Informed to Incentivised	2015	0.42	-0.12 (-0.15 to -0.1)*	0.03 (-0.06 to 0.11)	0.1 (0.08 to 0.11)*	0.1
Diagnostic adequacy of hypercholesterolemia			2015	0.17	-0.02 (-0.02 to -0.02)*	-0.02 (-0.07 to 0.02)	0.01 (0.003 to 0.03)*	0.09
Diagnostic adequacy of hypertension			2015	0.22	-0.04 (-0.04 to -0.04)*	-0.01 (-0.03 to 0.001)	0.03 (0.03 to 0.03)*	0.09
Diagnostic adequacy of obesity			2015	0.15	-0.05 (-0.05 to -0.04)*	0.01 (-0.02 to 0.04)	0.04 (0.03 to 0.04)*	0.02
Diagnostic adequacy of other health problems			2015	0.07	-0.02 (-0.02 to -0.01)*	0.01 (-0.01 to 0.03)	0.01 (0.01 to 0.01)*	0.03
Diagnostic adequacy of respiratory disease			2015	0.12	-0.03 (-0.03 to -0.02)*	0.01 (-0.01 to 0.03)	0.02 (0.02 to 0.02)*	0.05

Diagnostic quality of T2DM	Introduced as Informed	2015	0.01	-0.003 (-0.003 to -0.002)*	-1e-04 (-0.002 to 0.002)	0.003 (0.002 to 0.003)*	0.01	
Diagnostic adequacy of cardiovascular disease		2013	0.79	-0.07 (-0.09 to -0.04)*	-0.18 (-0.24 to -0.12)*	-0.05 (-0.08 to -0.03)*	0.29	
Diagnostic adequacy of hypertension		2013	0.24	0.01 (0.01 to 0.01)*	-0.06 (-0.06 to -0.06)*	-0.05 (-0.05 to -0.05)*	0.18	
Diagnostic adequacy of obesity		2013	0.2	-0.003 (-0.01 to 0)*	-0.04 (-0.04 to -0.03)*	-0.04 (-0.05 to -0.04)*	0.1	
Antiplatelet therapy in T2DM without cardiovascular disease		2017	0.28	0.002 (0.002 to 0.003)*	-0.03 (-0.03 to -0.02)*	-0.004 (-0.01 to -9e-04)*	0.27	
Diagnostic adequacy of hypercholesterolemia		2013	0.17	0.01 (0.005 to 0.01)*	-0.02 (-0.02 to -0.02)*	-0.02 (-0.03 to -0.02)*	0.15	
Diagnostic adequacy of respiratory disease		2013	0.16	-0.01 (-0.01 to -0.004)*	-0.02 (-0.02 to -0.01)*	-0.02 (-0.02 to -0.02)*	0.1	
Diagnostic quality of T2DM		2013	0.02	-0.003 (-0.003 to -0.002)*	-0.001 (-0.002 to -7e-04)*	0 (-2e-04 to 2e-04)	0.01	
Annual ECG in AF risk population		2017	0.13	0.01 (0.001 to 0.01)*	-0.02 (-0.05 to 0.01)	-0.02 (-0.03 to -0.01)*	0.14	
Diagnostic adequacy of other health problems		2013	0.12	-0.02 (-0.03 to -0.02)*	0.02 (0.01 to 0.03)*	0.003 (-0.002 to 0.01)	0.06	
Biennial heart rate measurement in individuals aged 60 or older		2017	0.24	-0.03 (-0.03 to -0.02)*	0.05 (0.02 to 0.08)*	0.03 (0.02 to 0.03)*	0.09	
Patients with excessive control of T2DM		2017	0.17	-0.01 (-0.02 to -0.01)*	0.02 (-3e-04 to 0.03)	0.01 (0.01 to 0.01)*	0.11	
T2DM: Screening for albuminuria		2017	0.37	-0.04 (-0.05 to -0.02)*	0.06 (-9e-04 to 0.11)	0.03 (0.01 to 0.04)*	0.11	
Good control of hypothyroidism	Derived	Introduced as Incentivized	2014	0.19	-4e-04 (-0.02 to 0.02)	-0.11 (-0.16 to -0.06)*	-0.004 (-0.02 to 0.02)	0.05
Blood pressure control in diabetes			2014	0.07	-0.01 (-0.01 to -0.01)*	6e-04 (-0.004 to 0.01)	0.005 (0.003 to 0.01)*	0.04
Blood pressure control in ischemic cardiopathy/cerebrovascular accident			2014	0.11	-0.01 (-0.01 to -0.01)*	0.01 (0.002 to 0.01)*	0.01 (0.01 to 0.01)*	0.06
LDL control in patients with high cardiovascular risk			2014	0.14	-0.01 (-0.01 to -0.01)*	0.002 (-0.01 to 0.01)	0.01 (0.01 to 0.02)*	0.1
LDL measurement in secondary prevention			Introduced as Informed	2018	0.09	-0.003 (-0.01 to 0)	0.01 (-0.01 to 0.02)	0.003 (-2e-04 to 0.01)
Smoking cessation in T2DM		2018		0.34	0.001 (-0.01 to 0.01)	0.01 (-0.04 to 0.06)	-0.01 (-0.02 to 9e-04)	0.3

ACE inhibitor treatment in T2DM with microalbuminuria			2017	0.22	-0.01 (-0.01 to -0.01)*	4e-04 (-0.02 to 0.02)	0.01 (0.01 to 0.02)*	0.16
Blood pressure measurement in cardiovascular disease			2018	0.07	-0.005 (-0.01 to -0.003)*	0.01 (0.004 to 0.02)*	0.002 (-4e-04 to 0.004)	0.04
Blood pressure measurement in T2DM			2017	0.06	-0.005 (-0.01 to -0.004)*	0.01 (0.01 to 0.01)*	0.003 (0.002 to 0.005)*	0.03
BMI measurement			2017	0.18	-0.02 (-0.02 to -0.01)*	0.03 (0.01 to 0.05)*	0.02 (0.01 to 0.02)*	0.09
HbA1c measurement			2017	0.05	-0.004 (-0.004 to -0.003)*	0.01 (0.003 to 0.01)*	0.001 (0 to 0.003)	0.03
LDL control in T2DM with high cardiovascular risk			2017	0.14	-0.01 (-0.01 to -0.004)*	0.02 (0.001 to 0.03)*	0.01 (0.01 to 0.02)*	0.09
LDL control in T2DM with ischemic cardiopathy/cerebrovascular accident			2017	0.13	-0.01 (-0.01 to -0.003)*	0.01 (0.002 to 0.02)*	0.002 (-0.001 to 0.01)	0.08
Physical activity in T2DM: sedentary individuals improving in the change stage			2017	0.63	-0.09 (-0.11 to -0.06)*	0.14 (0.02 to 0.26)*	0.11 (0.08 to 0.14)*	0.21
Tobacco abstinence in T2DM			2017	0.04	-9e-04 (-0.002 to 0)	0.01 (0.003 to 0.01)*	7e-04 (-8e-04 to 0.002)	0.03
Weight reduction in overweight and obese diabetic patients			2017	0.18	-0.01 (-0.01 to -0.01)*	0.02 (0.01 to 0.02)*	0.01 (0.01 to 0.01)*	0.13

† Inverse indicators (negative step and trend changes represent improvement); ‡ Introduced as Incentivised: baseline result 2010, end result 2019; Informed to Incentivised: baseline result 2013, end result 2019; Introduced as Informed: baseline result 2010, end result 2019 (except for diagnostic indicators, 2014); all derived indicators: baseline result 2010, end result 2019; * Coefficient different than zero with $p < 0.05$; **bold text** indicates positive impacts.

Annex Table 3 | Interrupted time series (ITS) analysis on average indicator results among ICS primary care practices for the indicators that did not change scheme, simulating an intervention in 2014.

Indicator	Derived	Scheme change	Year of simulated intervention	Baseline result (%)	Trend before scheme change (% pt change) (95% CI)	Step change (% pt change) (95% CI)	Change in trend (additional % pt change) (95% CI)	End result (%)
Screening for alcohol consumption	New	Always Incentivised	2014	49.25	2.52 (1.38 to 3.66)*	18.11 (8.33 to 27.89)*	-5.26 (-8.65 to -1.88)*	56.72
T2DM: Screening for diabetic foot				51.09	2.3 (2.23 to 2.37)*	2.19 (0.15 to 4.22)*	-1.03 (-1.53 to -0.54)*	68.68
Inhaler verification				60.43	4.13 (2.09 to 6.17)*	2.96 (-4.78 to 10.71)	-2.4 (-4.94 to 0.14)	88.69
T2DM: Retinopathy screening				66.28	1.45 (1.13 to 1.78)*	1.56 (-0.33 to 3.44)	-0.5 (-1.05 to 0.04)	77.68
Correct treatment of renal colic				92.47	0.04 (-0.04 to 0.12)	1.07 (-0.04 to 2.17)	-0.06 (-0.35 to 0.24)	93.45
Comprehensive assessment of individuals in home-based care				84.74	2.66 (2.11 to 3.22)*	-1.27 (-3.91 to 1.37)	-3.27 (-4.06 to -2.48)*	91.39
Dyslipidemia: Calculation of cardiovascular risk (35-74 years)				70.29	4.89 (3.79 to 5.98)*	-0.47 (-3.57 to 2.64)	-3.77 (-5 to -2.54)*	95.14
Hypertension: Blood pressure control				67.67	1.49 (0.99 to 1.99)*	-0.4 (-2.24 to 1.45)	-1.87 (-2.46 to -1.27)*	71.32
Hypertension: Blood pressure control in patients with chronic kidney disease				71.27	2.48 (1.96 to 3)*	1.04 (-1.32 to 3.4)	-1.81 (-2.48 to -1.14)*	84.77
LDL control in ischemic cardiopathy/cerebrovascular accident				48.08	3.76 (3.23 to 4.28)*	-3.15 (-5.25 to -1.05)*	-2.85 (-3.47 to -2.23)*	65.01
Pneumococcal vaccination coverage in individuals older than 64				68.31	-0.58 (-0.77 to -0.38)*	0.71 (-0.08 to 1.5)	-0.29 (-0.56 to -0.01)*	63.23
T2DM: HbA1C control				62.3	1.7 (1.37 to 2.02)*	-0.6 (-1.32 to 0.13)	-1.36 (-1.69 to -1.02)*	69.92
Treatment with ACE inhibitors or ARBs in heart failure, hypertension, or diabetes with nephropathy				73.9	0.98 (0.79 to 1.17)*	0.2 (-0.54 to 0.94)	-0.77 (-1 to -0.54)*	78.83
Treatment with beta-blockers for ischemic cardiopathy and heart failure				49.72	4.95 (4.64 to 5.27)*	-0.97 (-2.52 to 0.58)	-3.1 (-3.71 to -2.49)*	76.4
Inadequate long-acting beta-agonists in monotherapy in asthma†				Never Informed	32.9	-0.49 (-0.64 to -0.33)*	-0.17 (-0.88 to 0.54)	-0.23 (-0.49 to 0.04)
Inhaled glucocorticoids in persistent asthma	41.9	0.38 (0.12 to 0.65)*	0.65 (-0.05 to 1.35)		0.22 (-0.11 to 0.54)	47.18		

BMI recording in COPD with FEV1<50%				52.25	3.83 (-0.91 to 8.57)	-1.55 (-16.43 to 13.33)	-3.48 (-8.29 to 1.32)	62.45
Biennial spirometry in COPD				29.59	5.02 (3.6 to 6.43)*	4.37 (-0.5 to 9.24)	-6.75 (-8.34 to -5.17)*	45.11
Inadequate inhaled corticosteroids in monotherapy in COPD†				49.86	1.18 (1.11 to 1.26)*	0.6 (0.27 to 0.93)*	0.26 (0.14 to 0.39)*	37.34
Smokers older than 15 receiving anti-smoking advice				23.39	-0.1 (-0.68 to 0.48)	-1.65 (-3.17 to -0.14)*	-0.63 (-1.38 to 0.11)	18.04
Smoking cessation advice in COPD or asthma				34.22	0.76 (-0.58 to 2.09)	-2.81 (-6.12 to 0.51)	-1.69 (-3.19 to -0.19)*	29.9
Influenza vaccination in asthma and COPD	Derive d			33.1	-0.69 (-0.84 to -0.54)*	0.9 (-0.23 to 2.03)	0.09 (-0.46 to 0.65)	29.46
Smoking cessation in COPD				17.73	-0.88 (-1.35 to -0.42)*	1.1 (-2.28 to 4.48)	-0.25 (-1.2 to 0.69)	10.13
Tobacco abstinence in COPD or asthma				71.3	0.03 (-0.28 to 0.34)	-0.23 (-1.47 to 1)	-0.73 (-1.15 to -0.31)*	68.2

† Inverse indicators (negative step and trend changes represent improvement); * Coefficient different than zero with $p < 0.05$; **bold text** indicates positive impacts.

Annex Table 4 | Interrupted time series (ITS) analysis on the coefficient of variation (CV) of indicator results among ICS primary care practices for the indicators that did not change scheme, simulating an intervention in 2014.

Indicator	Derive d	Scheme change	Year of simulated intervention	Baseline result (%)	Trend before scheme change (annual CV change) (95% CI)	Step change (CV change) (95% CI)	Change in trend (additional CV change) (95% CI)	End result (%)
Screening for alcohol consumption	New	Always Incentivised	2014	0.17	-0.02 (-0.03 to -0.02)*	-0.04 (-0.07 to -0.01)*	0.03 (0.02 to 0.04)*	0.1
Correct treatment of renal colic				0.06	-0.001 (-0.002 to -7e-04)*	-0.002 (-0.01 to 0.01)	0 (-0.003 to 0.003)	0.05
Pneumococcal vaccination coverage in individuals older than 64				0.14	-0.003 (-0.004 to -0.002)*	-0.001 (-0.004 to 0.002)	0 (-0.001 to 0.001)	0.1
T2DM: Retinopathy screening				0.13	-0.01 (-0.01 to -0.003)*	-0.01 (-0.02 to 0.005)	-7e-04 (-0.005 to 0.003)	0.06
T2DM: HbA1C control				0.07	-0.002 (-0.005 to 0.002)	-0.01 (-0.02 to 0.01)	4e-04 (-0.003 to 0.004)	0.05
Treatment with ACE inhibitors or ARBs in heart failure, hypertension, or diabetes with nephropathy				0.06	-0.001 (-0.002 to 3e-04)	0.001 (-0.004 to 0.01)	-0.001 (-0.003 to 5e-04)	0.04
Comprehensive assessment of individuals in home-based care				0.12	-0.02 (-0.03 to -0.01)*	0.004 (-0.02 to 0.03)	0.03 (0.02 to 0.05)*	0.09
Dyslipidemia: Calculation of cardiovascular risk (35-74 years)				0.15	-0.03 (-0.04 to -0.03)*	0.01 (-0.01 to 0.02)	0.03 (0.02 to 0.03)*	0.01
Hypertension: Blood pressure control				0.08	-0.01 (-0.01 to -0.01)*	0.003 (-0.002 to 0.01)	0.01 (0.01 to 0.01)*	0.06
Hypertension: Blood pressure control in patients with chronic kidney disease				0.11	-0.01 (-0.02 to -0.01)*	-6e-04 (-0.01 to 0.01)	0.01 (0.01 to 0.01)*	0.04
Inhaler verification				0.38	-0.08 (-0.11 to -0.04)*	0.05 (-0.03 to 0.14)	0.07 (0.03 to 0.11)*	0.05
LDL control in ischemic cardiopathy/cerebrovascular accident				0.12	-0.01 (-0.02 to -0.01)*	0.02 (0.01 to 0.04)*	0.01 (0.01 to 0.02)*	0.07
T2DM: Screening for diabetic foot				0.29	-0.05 (-0.06 to -0.05)*	0.03 (0.02 to 0.05)*	0.04 (0.04 to 0.05)*	0.07
Treatment with beta-blockers for ischemic cardiopathy and heart failure				0.16	-0.01 (-0.01 to -0.01)*	-0.003 (-0.01 to 0.003)	0.003 (0.001 to 0.01)*	0.09
Inadequate inhaled corticosteroids in monotherapy in COPD	Never Informe d			0.12	0.003 (0.002 to 0.004)*	0.01 (-7e-04 to 0.02)	-3e-04 (-0.003 to 0.002)	0.16

Biennial spirometry in COPD	Derive d			0.47	-0.04 (-0.07 to -0.01)*	-0.07 (-0.17 to 0.03)	0.05 (0.02 to 0.09)*	0.33
BMI recording in COPD with FEV1<50%				0.45	-0.05 (-0.11 to 0.01)	0.01 (-0.18 to 0.19)	0.06 (0.001 to 0.12)*	0.34
Inadequate long-acting beta-agonists in monotherapy in asthma				0.15	-0.01 (-0.01 to -0.01)*	0.005 (0.003 to 0.01)*	0.003 (0.003 to 0.004)*	0.11
Inhaled glucocorticoids in persistent asthma				0.12	-0.005 (-0.01 to -0.004)*	0.01 (0.004 to 0.01)*	0.004 (0.003 to 0.01)*	0.1
Smokers older than 15 receiving anti-smoking advice				0.46	-0.04 (-0.08 to 0.004)	0.01 (-0.11 to 0.13)	0.05 (0.004 to 0.09)*	0.38
Smoking cessation advice in COPD or asthma				0.42	-0.03 (-0.07 to 0.01)	0.01 (-0.1 to 0.12)	0.04 (4e-04 to 0.08)*	0.35
Tobacco abstinence in COPD or asthma				0.07	-0.002 (-0.003 to 0)*	0.002 (-0.002 to 0.01)	0.002 (-2e-04 to 0.003)	0.06
Influenza vaccination in asthma and COPD				0.21	-0.002 (-0.01 to 0.001)	0.002 (-0.01 to 0.01)	0.002 (-0.004 to 0.01)	0.18
Smoking cessation in COPD				0.39	-0.01 (-0.02 to -0.01)*	-0.01 (-0.03 to 0.02)	0.02 (0.01 to 0.03)*	0.35

* Coefficient different than zero with $p < 0.05$; **bold text** indicates positive impacts.

Annex 2 – Supplementary material from the study on the impact of information provision and financial incentives in the recovery of primary care quality after a health system shock (COVID-19 pandemic)

Annex Table 2.1 | Relation of indicators included in the study.

Indicator name	Internal code	Indicator type	Indicator scheme	Description
Appropriate treatment of atrial fibrillation	EQA0201	Treatment	Kept as incentivised	% of the assigned population aged 15 to 90 years diagnosed with atrial fibrillation (AF) who have an appropriate indication for anticoagulant treatment based on their thromboembolic risk (CHA ₂ DS ₂ -VASc score) and their bleeding risk assessed using the HAS-BLED score.
Antiplatelet treatment in ischemic cardiopathy/cerebrovascular accident	EQA0203	Treatment		% of the assigned population over 14 years of age with a diagnosis of ischemic stroke and/or ischemic heart disease who have a documented current treatment with an antiplatelet and/or anticoagulant agent.
LDL control in ischemic cardiopathy/cerebrovascular accident	EQA0204	Control		% of the assigned population, aged 14 to 80, diagnosed with ischemic cardiopathy / cerebrovascular accident, who had the latest LDL cholesterol determination ≤ 120 mg/dl in the last year.
Blood pressure control in ischemic cardiopathy/cerebrovascular accident	EQA0205	Control		% of the assigned population, aged 14 to 80, diagnosed with ischemic heart disease and/or stroke, in which the BP during the last year is equal to or less than: (1) 24-hour BP values by Ambulatory Blood Pressure Monitoring (ABPM) ≤ 130/80 mmHg; (2) 24-hour BP values by Home Blood Pressure Monitoring (HBPM) ≤ 135/85 mmHg; (3) Average of the last 3 clinical BP measurements ≤ 140/90 mmHg.
Treatment with ACE inhibitors or ARBs in heart failure, hypertension, or diabetes with nephropathy	EQA0207	Treatment		% of the assigned population, aged 14 to 90, diagnosed with congestive heart failure or nephropathy/chronic kidney disease with hypertension or T2DM, who are receiving treatment with ACE inhibitors (ARB inhibitors in case of intolerance).
T2DM: Screening for diabetic foot	EQA0208	Screening		% of the assigned population, aged 14 to 80, diagnosed with T2DM, who have been screened for diabetic foot in the last year.

T2DM: HbA1C control	EQA0209	Control		% of the assigned population, aged 14 to 80, diagnosed with T2DM, in which the last determination of glycated hemoglobin in the last year is $\leq 8\%$.
T2DM: Retinopathy screening	EQA0210	Screening		% of the assigned population, aged 14 to 80, diagnosed with T2DM, who have undergone retinopathy screening in the last 2 years.
Blood pressure control in diabetes	EQA0212	Control		% of the assigned population, aged 14 to 80, diagnosed with T2DM, in which the BP during the last year is equal to or less than: (1) 24-hour BP values by Ambulatory Blood Pressure Monitoring $\leq 140/85$ mmHg; (2) 24-hour BP values by Home Blood Pressure Monitoring $\leq 145/90$ mmHg; (3) Average of the last 3 clinical BP measurements $\leq 150/95$ mmHg.
Hypertension: Blood pressure control	EQA0213	Control		% of the assigned population, aged 14 to 80, diagnosed with arterial hypertension, who had a BP measurement during the last year equal or less than: (1) 24-hour BP values by Ambulatory BP Monitoring $\leq 140/85$ mmHg ($\leq 145/90$ if older than 60); (2) 24-hour BP values by Home BP Monitoring $\leq 145/90$ mmHg ($\leq 145/90$ if older than 60); (3) Average of the last 3 clinical BP measurements $\leq 150/95$ mmHg ($\leq 160/95$ if older than 60).
Good control of hypothyroidism	EQA0227	Control		% of the assigned population, aged 14 to 80, with hypothyroidism, who have the latest TSH < 10 in the last 18 months.
Hypertension: Blood pressure control in patients with chronic kidney disease	EQA0235	Control		% of the assigned population, aged 14 to 80, diagnosed with arterial hypertension (HTA) and chronic kidney disease (CKD), in which the BP during the last year is: (1) the last 24-hour ambulatory BP monitoring value is equal to or less than 140/85 mmHg; (2) the last 24-hour home BP monitoring value is equal to or less than 145/90 mmHg; (3) the average of the last 3 BP measurements is equal to or less than 150/95 mmHg.
Comprehensive assessment of individuals in home-based care	EQA0401	Screening		% of the assigned and attended population over 14 years of age enrolled in the home-based care program for 30 days or more, who have received a comprehensive assessment..
LDL control in patients with high cardiovascular risk	EQA0214	Control	Incentivized in 2023	% of the assigned population, aged 35 to 74, with cardiovascular risk (REGICOR) $\geq 10\%$ at 10 years, who had an LDL cholesterol measure ≤ 150 mg/dl in the last 18 months.
Dyslipidemia: Calculation of cardiovascular	EQA0215	Screening		% of the assigned population, aged 35 to 74, diagnosed with hypercholesterolemia, who had cardiovascular risk (CV) measured

risk (35-74 years)				using the REGICOR method at least once since the diagnosis.
Monitoring of new cases of iron-deficiency anemia	EQA0219	Follow-up		% of new diagnoses of iron-deficiency anemia lasting more than 3 months and active during the evaluation period, in individuals aged 14 to 80 years, for whom follow-up hemoglobin and ferritin values are recorded between 3 and 6 months after diagnosis.
Inhaler verification	EQA0220	Follow-up		% of the assigned population, aged 14 to 80, diagnosed with COPD or bronchiectasis and treated with inhalers, who were provided documentation of training or assessment of inhaler technique.
Correct treatment of renal colic	EQA0223	Treatment		% of the assigned population, aged 14 to 90, with a new diagnosis of renal colic in the last year, in which the prescribed analgesic treatment regimen does not include N-butyrylhyoscine (Buscopan).
Correct treatment of asymptomatic hyperuricemia	EQA0224	Treatment		% of the assigned population, aged 14 to 90, with asymptomatic hyperuricemia, who have not been treated with urate-lowering agents.
Treatment adequacy in acute tonsillitis	EQA0226	Treatment		% of the assigned population, aged 14 to 90, with newly diagnosed acute tonsillitis (in the last 3 months), who have not undergone antibiotic treatment or with treatment with penicillin (or equivalent).
Adequacy of treatment in acute gastroenteritis	EQA0229	Treatment		% of the assigned population, aged 14 to 70, newly diagnosed with acute gastroenteritis during the last year, in which antibiotic treatment has not been prescribed during the 72 hours following the diagnosis.
Appropriateness of urinary tract infection treatment	EQA0230	Treatment		% of new diagnoses of urinary tract infection (UTI) in assigned and attended women aged 14 to 90 years who received appropriate antibiotic treatment.
Appropriateness of treatment for non-suppurative acute otitis media	EQA0231	Treatment		% of new diagnoses of acute non-suppurative otitis media in assigned and attended patients aged 14 to 90 years for whom no antibiotic treatment was prescribed or amoxicillin treatment was prescribed.
Adequacy of treatment for acute bronchitis, acute rhinopharyngitis, and influenza	EQA0232	Treatment		% of new diagnoses of acute bronchitis, acute rhinopharyngitis, and influenza during the last year, in the assigned population aged 14 to 90, for whom antibiotic treatment has not been prescribed.

Abstainers in at-risk population	EQA0304	Control	% of assigned and attended population aged 14 to 80 years with a diagnosis of ischemic heart disease (IHD), T2DM, asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), heart failure (HF), HTA, or undergoing hormonal contraception treatment, for whom non-smoking status has been documented during the evaluation period (with the recommended frequency).
Hepatitis C vaccination: anti-HBV and anti-HAV vaccination	EQA0310	Vaccination	% of assigned and attended population aged 15 years or older with a diagnosis of chronic hepatitis C who have been immunized against hepatitis A and hepatitis B.
Assessment of pressure ulcer risk in individuals receiving home care	EQA0402	Screening	% of patients over 14 years of age enrolled in the home care program with a Barthel score <40, for whom the risk of pressure ulcers has been assessed using the Braden Scale at least once during the evaluation period.
Achieving a safe home environment for individuals receiving home care	EQA0403	Screening	% of patients over 14 years of age enrolled in the home care program who have received interventions aimed at achieving a safe home environment.
Caregiver burden in patients receiving home care	EQA0404	Screening	% of patients over 14 years of age enrolled in the home care program with an identified caregiver, for whom the caregiver burden scale (Zarit scale score) has been administered.
Dental review in T2DM with poor glycemic control	EQA0602	Screening	% of the population aged 15 to 80 years with a diagnosis of T2DM and at least one determination of glycated hemoglobin during the evaluation period greater than 8%, who have undergone a dental examination in the past two years.
Diagnostic adequacy of cardiovascular disease	EQD0238	Diagnosis	% of the assigned population, older than 14, diagnosed with heart failure, who have been assessed with an ECG the year prior or after diagnosis, who have their functional level of heart failure described, and whose type of heart failure has been registered according to the corresponding registry codes.
Diagnostic quality of T2DM	EQD0239	Diagnosis	% of the assigned population, older than 14, taking non-insulin antidiabetic medications, who are diagnosed with T2DM and who fulfil the T2DM diagnostic criteria.

Diagnostic adequacy of hypertension	EQD0240	Diagnosis	% of the assigned population, older than 14, with a hypertension diagnosis in the last year, in any of the following cases: (1) The average of the last 3 blood pressure measurements before diagnosis exceeds 140/90 mmHg; (2) Pathological home blood pressure monitoring or ambulatory blood pressure monitoring; (3) Who do not have any abnormal blood pressure measurements before the diagnosis of HTA, but have one subsequent measurement within a maximum period of 3 months from the diagnosis.
Diagnostic adequacy of hypercholesterolemia	EQD0241	Diagnosis	% of the assigned population, older than 14, diagnosed with hypercholesterolemia in the last year, who have had any determination of total cholesterol ≥ 250 mg/dl.
Diagnostic adequacy of respiratory disease	EQD0242	Diagnosis	Aggregate of the following: % of the assigned population, older than 14, (1) being treated with bronchodilators, who have a chronic respiratory obstruction or asthma; (2) diagnosed with COPD in the last year, who have a FEV1/FVC < 0.7 registered 1 year before or 6 months after diagnosis (3) newly diagnosed with asthma who have been assessed with a spirometry with bronchodilator test; (4) with an obstructive spirometry who have a diagnosis of chronic respiratory obstruction; (5) with asthma who have a register of the severity degree.
Diagnostic adequacy of other health problems	EQD0247	Diagnosis	Aggregate of the following: % of the assigned population, older than 14, (1) with a newly diagnoses ferropenic anemia who have had a determination of hemoglobin and ferritin; (2) taking anti-osteoporotic medications who have a diagnosis of osteoporosis, Paget's disease, or multiple myeloma; (3) with a new diagnosis of osteoporosis who have a bone mineral density test consistent with osteoporosis or a fragility fracture; (4) with a new diagnosis of hypothyroidism who have a TSH level above 4 mU/L between the 12 months prior to the diagnosis and the following 6 months; (5) treated with anti-migraine drugs who have a diagnosis of migraine; (6) prescribed diapers who have a diagnosis of urinary incontinence or fecal incontinence; (7) diagnosed with dementia who have a cognitive test; (8) diagnosed with chronic kidney disease who have an estimated glomerular filtration rate lower than 60 or a

				urinary albumin-to-creatinine ratio greater than 30.
Diagnostic adequacy of obesity	of EQD0313	Diagnosis		Aggregate of the following: % of the assigned population, older than 14, (1) newly diagnosed with obesity, who have a BMI >30 a year before or 6 months after diagnosis; (2) who have a BMI >30 in the last 18 months and have been diagnosed with obesity.

Annex Table 2.2 | Description of indicator types and the activities associated with them.

Indicator type	Number of indicators in the study	Description of the activity
<i>Control</i>	9	These indicators measure the % of patients with a specific disease/condition whose clinical results show that their disease is being correctly managed (e.g., the % of patients with hypertension who keep low values of blood pressure).
<i>Follow-up</i>	2	These indicators measure the % of patients with a disease/condition who have received a recommended clinical action aimed at monitoring the disease or its treatment (e.g., the % of EPOC and asthmatic patients whose inhaler administration technique has been assessed).
<i>Diagnosis</i>	7	These indicators measure the % of population who have been diagnosed of a specific disease and fulfil the necessary criteria (e.g. % of people diagnosed with obesity with a body mass index > 30).
<i>Screening</i>	8	Related to the % of the population at risk of a specific disease/complication, who have been screened for it (e.g., the % of diabetic population who have been screened for the diabetic foot).
<i>Treatment</i>	10	These indicators show the % of the population with a disease who are being treated correctly according to specific criteria (e.g. % of patients with atrial fibrillation whose treatment is correctly tailored based on their risk to suffer a thromboembolic or hemorrhagic accident).
<i>Vaccination</i>	1	These capture the % of patients at risk who have been vaccinated against a specific disease (e.g. hepatitis C patients vaccinated against hepatitis A and B).

Annex Table 2.3 | Bivariate analysis of the association between PCP/indicator-level variables with incentive schemes.

	Late- incentivised	Early- incentivised	p.overall
	<i>N=3,953</i>	<i>N=3,114</i>	
% result drop	15.9 (16.0)	29.1 (18.1)	<0.001
Indicator type:			0
Control	415 (10.5%)	1,973 (63.4%)	
Diagnosis	1,396 (35.3%)	0 (0.00%)	
Follow-up	461 (11.7%)	0 (0.00%)	
Screening	1,032 (26.1%)	826 (26.5%)	
Treatment	649 (16.4%)	315 (10.1%)	
MEDEA socioeconomic deprivation index			0.944
1U	628 (15.9%)	488 (15.7%)	
2U	536 (13.6%)	420 (13.5%)	
3U	646 (16.4%)	523 (16.8%)	
4U	803 (20.4%)	612 (19.7%)	
Rural	1,340 (33.9%)	1,071 (34.4%)	
N patients	18,194 (8,011)	18,274 (8,113)	0.679
Age of patients	49.0 (1.92)	49.0 (1.91)	0.448
% female patients	50.6 (2.17)	50.6 (2.16)	0.452
% immigrant patients	18.5 (9.06)	18.5 (9.04)	0.704
N professionals	26.5 (9.88)	26.6 (10.0)	0.73
N general practitioners	13.2 (5.03)	13.3 (5.10)	0.778
N nurses	13.2 (4.90)	13.3 (4.99)	0.683

N represents the total number of observations (in the second row, the total number of indicator-PCP observations in each group). MEDEA classification stratifies urban PCPs according to the socioeconomic deprivation of the area they serve, ranked from 1U to 4U (from less to more deprived, respectively).